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How insecticide-treated nets (ITNs) work: The biological mechanisms by which ITNs give personal- and community-level protection against malaria

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How insecticide-treated nets (ITNs) work: The biological mechanisms by which ITNs give personal- and community-level protection against malaria

Jo Lines, Nakul Chitnis and Lucy Paintain

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Background

The public health value of pyrethroid-only ITNs was comprehensively demonstrated through numerous cluster randomized trials conducted between 1988 and 2013. Some (but not all) of the early trials observed that with high coverage, the ITNs protected not only the ITN-users, but also other people in the same village not using a net. This phenomenon, which has subsequently become known as the ‘community effect’ of ITNs, is mediated by area-wide effects on the local vector mosquito population. These effects are similar to those of indoor-residual spraying. However, a key point to note is that in those early ITN trials, the community effect was variable: in one trial it was absent, while in several others, it was contributing a substantial fraction of the protection observed in villages with ITNs.

Since then, entomologists have developed a clear understanding of the biological mechanisms underlying this phenomenon, and its variability. This understanding emerged from detailed studies of the entomological effects of ITNs, and now makes up a major component of the mathematical models used to describe parasite transmission and to compare the effects of alternative intervention strategies. However, the evidence that gave rise to this “mechanistic understanding” is not as widely known as it should be, and it has never been comprehensively reviewed.

This review therefore addresses the question “How do ITNs work?”, or more precisely: “What are the biological mechanisms by which ITNs give personal- and community-level protection against malaria?”

The ento-epidemiological theory of how ITNs work

ITNs¹ protect in two ways. First, the user is isolated from the mosquito population outside; this gives personal protection. The strength of this personal protection is affected by vector behaviour and how the net is used, and it also depends on the integrity of the net and the immediate effects of the insecticide on host-seeking mosquitoes. However, from the user’s perspective, it is independent of coverage.

¹ including LLINs

Second, the presence of ITNs in a community may alter the local mosquito population, reducing its 'vectorial capacity' (its ability to transmit the parasite). Various effects on vector biology and behaviour have been observed, but the most important for vectorial capacity is the insecticidal killing of host-seeking female vectors as they try to feed on someone under an ITN. This has a very powerful effect on transmission because (a) the risk is repeated in every gonotrophic cycle, and (b) it takes the parasite 9 to 11 days (i.e. 3 or 4 gonotrophic cycles) to mature inside the mosquito. This means that a modest increase in the probability of being killed in each cycle causes a major reduction in the probability of surviving to the age at which a female can be infective. This is known as the community effect or the mass effect of ITNs.

The community effect is more or less the same as the mode of action of indoor-residual spraying (IRS), as first described in the 1950s. It depends on the probability that a female will be killed as she tries to feed. It therefore depends on some vector-related factors, such the innate host-preference of the vector species, and the insecticide resistance genes that may have evolved in the local vector population. It also depends on some features of the intervention: ITN coverage, the residual insecticidal activity of the net (given its age and washing history), etc.

Measuring the Community Effect: Experimental Huts and Epidemiological trials

These ento-epidemiological modes of action can be measured at the household level in entomological terms, but this requires experimental huts and cannot be done in ordinary houses. Personal protection can be measured in epidemiological terms by comparing epidemiological outcomes between ITN users and non-users within the same community. The community effect can be measured by comparing non-net-users in high-ITN-coverage-communities and those in communities without ITNs.

Findings of a systematic review of evidence comparing personal- and community-level protection of ITNs

We updated the search results of the 2018 Cochrane review by Pryce et al on the efficacy of ITNs for preventing malaria to July 2020. We explored what evidence was available from randomised clinical trials to understand the contributions of personal protection and community-level effects towards effectiveness of ITNs in different settings. In total, 31 papers on 21 studies were included in our review. Of the 21 studies considered, five were individually-randomised and so could only provide evidence on the personal protection offered by ITNs, and sixteen reported per protocol analyses of a cRCT, providing evidence on the combined personal and community effects of ITNs. Four of the sixteen cRCTs also reported epidemiological outcomes in such a way that personal and community effects of ITN use could be separated. Of the seven studies that reported entomological outcomes, five had data suitable to assess whether there was a

community effect or not, namely a measure of vector abundance, sporozoite rate and entomological inoculation rate.

A total of six of the 21 studies included in this review reported results in a way suitable to assess community effect separately to personal protection – either through epidemiological outcomes, entomological outcomes, or both. Outcomes were too diverse to support a meta-analysis. Instead, data synthesis was used to integrate the evidence from these six studies. Overall, four of the six studies reported presence of epidemiological and/or entomological evidence for a community effect: in Ghana, coastal Kenya, western Kenya and Sierra Leone. Evidence of a community effect was absent for two studies from The Gambia. There was a low risk of bias for all four studies contributing epidemiological data (Binka et al., 1996, D'Alessandro et al., 1995a, Nevill et al., 1996, Phillips-Howard et al., 2003). There is substantial risk of bias in some outcome measures from the entomological studies due to the methods of mosquito capture. However overall, we can have reasonable confidence in the entomological evidence from three of the five studies considered (Gimnig et al., 2003a, Gimnig et al., 2003b, Magbity et al., 1997, Thomson et al., 1995a, Thomson et al., 1995b), but not the other two (Mbogo et al., 1996, Lindsay et al., 1989).

Differences in the findings of the six studies included in the data synthesis support the importance of contextual factors on the likely strength of community effect. A particular question of interest is 'What is so different about The Gambia that means a community effect was not evident in this setting?' Two hypotheses are offered by the authors of those studies: it is possible that the net material influenced the killing effect of the insecticide as the intervention in The Gambia was to re-treat people's existing nets, some of which will have been cotton rather than synthetic (compared to the other trials which distributed and re-treated nylon or polyester nets). Another reason offered by the authors is that treated and untreated villages were interspersed and vectors were able to move between them which would mask any potential community effect on malaria transmission.

On balance, judging across all of the GRADE domains and considering the epidemiological and entomological evidence base as a whole, we are confident that the certainty of evidence from the six studies in the data synthesis is high. This evidence base supports that a community effect of ITNs on malaria transmission can happen and that there is a dose response with ITN coverage.

Factors Moderating the Community Effect.

The community effect arises because, when a substantial number of people are using ITNs, female mosquitoes risk being killed whenever they seek a bloodmeal. The size of this risk presumably varies with:

- Species-specific host-preference
- Relative availability of non-human and human hosts
- ITN Coverage (including usage)
- The nature of the insecticide: its residual insecticidal activity (and hence age of ITNs) and repellency
- Genes for resistance to insecticide(s) on net

It has sometimes been argued that there are some important thresholds of coverage associated with the community effect: for example the idea that some minimum-level of coverage must be achieved before the community is useful. In fact, there are no such coverage thresholds. For example, consider a long-lived anthropophilic vector such as *Anopheles gambiae* ss. What happens, in round-number-terms, when we increase coverage? The answer is that every additional 20% increase in coverage of the human population (from 20% to 40%, or 40% to 60%, or 60% to 80%) is expected to produce a further halving (approximately 50% reduction) in malaria transmission intensity (measured as EIR). Thus, right across this range, modest increases in coverage give substantially improved impact on transmission. Conversely, modest reductions in effective coverage do result in higher transmission and loss of control.

Remaining Knowledge Gaps

Although we know that the community effect must vary with the factors listed above, we have made surprisingly little effort to study this variation as it happens in practice and in the field. In particular, in the early days of ITN research, we neglected the need to carry out epidemiological field trials in settings outside Africa, with vectors showing a range of behaviours. Particularly worrying, given the current resistance situation in Africa, is the fact that we have so little data on the effect of resistance on the epidemiological effectiveness of ITNs – especially its impact on the community effect.

Conclusion

There is no doubt that the community effect can and does happen. There is now a remarkable consensus between malaria entomologists and epidemiological modellers about the ento-epidemiological mechanisms that mediate the protection given by ITNs: personal protection and community-level effects on transmission. Various contextual factors can influence the magnitude of the community effect. These include vector behaviour (particularly degree of anthropophily), level of ITN use, insecticide lethality, and insecticide resistance. With an anthropophilic vector, the community effect brings significant area-wide benefits range across the range of practicable coverage from 15% to 85%: there is no required minimum level of coverage, and additional coverage is always beneficial.

INTRODUCTION

Recent reductions in the global burden of malaria are attributable mainly to vector control, in particular insecticide-treated nets (ITNs) (Bhatt et al., 2015). However, these gains are not permanent: they will be lost if we fail to sustain coverage with effective interventions, and the moment they are threatened by insecticide resistance in African vectors and funding constraints. Hence, it is important to deploy ITNs so as to maximise their epidemiological benefits.

In the early epidemiological trials of ITNs, in the 1990s, the nets were in most cases deployed with full coverage of all residents in intervention villages. The Cochrane review summarising these trials was first published in 1998 (Lengeler, 1998), and the following year, an economic analysis estimated that ITNs were outstandingly cost-effective as child-survival intervention (Goodman et al., 1999). The first clear recommendation for large-scale ITN deployment came in 2000, with Roll Back Malaria's "Abuja Declaration". This announced some ambitious intervention coverage targets, including the idea that "60% of those at risk of malaria, particularly pregnant women and children under five years of age", should be protected with ITNs or an effective alternative. The Declaration said nothing about how ITNs should be distributed, but for the next few years, most ITN-distribution projects were strongly or exclusively focused on increasing coverage among pregnant women and under-fives. This strategy of 'targeting to vulnerable groups' made sense as an initial strategy, for two reasons: (a) the funding and distribution mechanisms available in the year 2000 were clearly inadequate to provide instant ITN-coverage for all the 500m people at risk in Africa, and (b) in the epidemiological conditions of the time, pregnant women and under-five children were suffering more than 85% of the burden of malaria mortality (Carneiro et al., 2010). There was little discussion of the question of whether this coverage strategy, covering vulnerable groups but not others in the community, would give ITN-users as much protection as that reported in the epidemiological trials, where there had been much higher levels of population coverage.

In the early 2000s, it became possible, with financial support from the recently-launched Global Fund for Aids TB and Malaria, to procure ITNs by the million and give them away for free in mass-distribution campaigns. At first, such campaigns were targeted to under-five children and delivered through measles-vaccine catch-up campaigns (Grabowsky et al., 2005). These were so successful that national-scale campaigns soon followed. By 2005, there was growing confidence in the Global Fund as a financing mechanism, and growing advocacy for the idea that covering a majority of the residents in a community was necessary in order to give adequate protection to the vulnerable sub-groups (Curtis et al., 2003, Killeen and Smith, 2007).

During this period, WHO had been actively promoting the development of long-lasting insecticidal nets (LLINs), and it announced in the 2007 “ITN position statement” (WHO, 2007) that malaria control programmes should now buy and distribute LLINs, not ITNs, and that the aim should be to achieve “full coverage of all people at risk of malaria” in the target area. To explain this altered recommendation, it was pointed out that high ITN coverage can give protection to everyone in the area, including those not under a net.

More broadly, over the years, there have been various suggestions that there might be a minimum threshold of coverage, below which ITNs are ineffective or not fully effective, and also a maximum threshold, above which further increases in coverage may not be cost-effective.

To address these questions, we must focus on the direct entomological effects of the intervention on mosquitoes, and the biological mechanisms by which these lead on to effects on malaria parasite transmission, and on epidemiological outcomes in humans. In the case of ITNs, these various “ento-epidemiological” mechanisms can be divided into two categories. First, there are the barrier mechanisms that tend to isolate the occupants of an ITN from whatever mosquitoes may be outside. The epidemiological consequence is that the individuals inside are given some “personal protection”. Then, there are the mechanisms that produce population-level changes in the local mosquito population, making it less dangerous by reducing its capacity to transmit malaria, its *vectorial capacity*. This gives area-wide epidemiological protection to everyone in the neighbourhood, and is usually called the “community effect” or “mass effect”.

Our knowledge of these ento-epidemiological mechanisms started with Macdonald’s analysis of malaria transmission. These mechanisms comprise a major component of the mathematical models that are used to analyse the effects of interventions on transmission, and to compare the expected effects of alternative integrated malaria control strategies. Entomologists and modellers now have a shared understanding of these mechanisms is familiar to less well-known amongst other malariologists, and has never been comprehensively reviewed.

The aim of this paper, therefore, is to summarise our current understanding of how ITNs work through personal protection and community effects and which contextual factors play an important role, with particular focus on the effects of scale and coverage (use).

We start with an overview of the biological picture that emerged from the early experimental hut and village-trials of ITNs; this provides the theoretical framework for the rest of the paper. We go on to focus on the techniques and indicators needed to measure personal protection and the community effect separately from each other. We report the results of a systematic review of epidemiological field trials, summarising the studies where the community effect and/or personal protection were measured separately from each other and synthesising the available evidence for (or against) a community effect of ITNs. We consider how these two protective mechanisms (personal protection versus community effect) are expected to vary from place to place and with coverage, and propose a new and simplified way to describe, for operational purposes, how much additional epidemiological benefit is to be expected from further increases in coverage. Finally, we consider the question of how these two mechanisms are affected by insecticide resistance. We conclude with some comments on the remaining gaps in our knowledge of the community effects of ITNs.

SECTION 1: Ento-epidemiological Mechanisms of Vector Control Impact and Methods of Measurement

1.1 Introduction

This concept of “ento-epidemiological mode of action” refers to the causal chain of biological processes, linking the immediate and direct entomological effects of the intervention on vectors, with the intermediate effects on pathogen transmission, and the eventual beneficial impact on human health. Many vector control technologies – including new ones such as ivermectin -- can affect vectorial capacity through more than one mechanism operating at different scales, and we believe this concept will be useful for thinking about scale, coverage and delivery systems for these new technologies.

1.2 Developing techniques to distinguish between effects of vector control on feeding and survival

It seems that the questions discussed in this paper are likely to arise with any form of vector control deployed at individual or household level. Indeed, these questions have been asked before, about indoor residual spraying (IRS) with dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane (DDT), and specific techniques were developed to address them.

In the late 1940s, when IRS with DDT was first being tested, Macdonald was developing his model summarising all the factors that influence the rate of parasite transmission (R_0) (Macdonald, 1952). His great insight was that the parameter to which transmission is most sensitive is vector longevity (the probability of surviving one day). Vector longevity is important because, in tropical conditions, the time taken for the parasite to mature inside the mosquito is longer than the lifespan of most female anopheline mosquitoes. In other words, even with a relatively long-lived species like *Anopheles gambiae*, only the longest-surviving minority of females are responsible for all the transmission (Magesa et al., 1991). Hence, a small number of a long-lived vector species can be more dangerous than a much larger number of a short-lived species. And, as Macdonald realised, an intervention that can produce even modest reductions in the probability of daily survival has large and amplified effects on the intensity of transmission.

When the entomological effects of DDT-spraying were investigated, it was observed that DDT reduced the numbers of vector mosquitoes in houses, but the size of this reduction depended on the sampling method used (Thomson, 1947). There was a moderate reduction in biting on sleepers inside sprayed rooms, but a much greater reduction in the number of fed females resting indoors on the wall after feeding. Such indoor-resting fed females would normally be abundant, but after spraying they almost completely disappeared. Hence, if one was trying to estimate the effect of a spraying campaign on vector population size, it would be misleading to rely only on counts of indoor-resting females. It is important to note that this “induced exophily” was clearly not inherited or evolved; it was not behavioural resistance. Rather it was a phenotypic and immediate response that occurred in sprayed but not unsprayed rooms. Thus, we discovered that the excito-repellent effects of DDT could have complex and dose-dependent effects, altering the mosquitoes’ behaviour in relation to our sampling methods, as well as their ability to transmit.

These observations highlighted the need to measure separately, and with as little bias as possible, to what degree DDT was preventing mosquitoes from feeding on the occupants of a sprayed house, and to what degree it was killing them. This cannot be done in ordinary houses, for several reasons including (a) an unknown proportion of females exit the house before or after feeding, and (b) the bodies of mosquitoes killed by the insecticide are removed before morning by ants. So, in the 1960s, new designs of experimental hut were introduced to overcome these problems: verandah-trap (Smith and Webley, 1969) and louver-trap huts (Silver, 2008). These are designed to allow mosquitoes to enter and leave more or less as they would in ordinary houses, while allowing estimation of:

- Deterrence = reduction in the number of unfed females entering during the night to seek a bloodmeal;
- Feeding inhibition = of those that enter, a reduced proportion succeed in obtaining a bloodmeal.

- Mortality = of those that enter, an increased proportion are killed; this is seen in both unfed and fed females, and in those that exit during the night as well as those that remain.
- Induced exophily = a much higher proportion of fed females leave the house before morning (instead of resting indoors to digest the bloodmeal, as many or most normally would).

So, when pyrethroid ITNs first appeared, these experimental huts were the obvious tool to use for initial evaluation.

It was clear from the first couple of studies with ITNs that both repellent and killing effects could be important, and that their relative importance might vary. The first study, by Darriet et al (Darriet et al., 1984) in Burkina Faso, showed that cotton nets treated with permethrin (80mg/m²) gave good protection to the sleepers in the hut. In this case, the protection was mediated mainly by deterrence, that is, through a reduction in the number of mosquitoes entering the huts to feed. Once inside, however, most female mosquitos fed successfully in this study, and only a small proportion were killed by the insecticide. The second trial, carried out in Tanzania, used permethrin-treated synthetic-fibre nets. In this study, there was only a slight deterrence (a small reduction in the number entering), but on the other hand, there was a large reduction in the proportion feeding, and substantial mortality (approx. 50%) due to the insecticide (Lines et al., 1987).

Since then, many experimental hut studies have been conducted, with a wide variety of nets in experimental huts of various designs in West and East Africa, and a wide range of results have been reported (Silver, 2008). Nevertheless, the levels of mortality observed with ITNs in experimental huts are broadly comparable to those seen with IRS spraying with DDT and other insecticides. Moreover, when we see this kind of killing in an experimental hut, it is reasonable to assume that the risk of being killed in this way is a repeated risk, it is something that female vectors must encounter every time they try to feed in an area where many people are using ITNs. In other words, it is exactly the kind of cumulative risk that causes a reduction in vector longevity. For this reason, the authors of the first Tanzanian experimental hut study of ITNs speculated that “Widespread use of treated nets in a community could therefore reduce the longevity, and hence the vectorial capacity, of the local mosquito population” (Lines et al., 1987).

So, this is how the story about experimental huts links back to the contrast between “personal protection” and the “community effect”; this is how we trace the two ento-epidemiological mechanisms by which the direct effect of ITNs on mosquitoes lead to the eventual epidemiological benefits. Using the experimental huts, we can quantify the degree to which the sleepers in the huts are protected from biting by whatever mosquitoes may be outside. This is a direct estimate of personal protection. We can also quantify the

probability that a hungry mosquito entering the hut will pick up a lethal dose of insecticide, before or after it feeds. This gives us an estimate of the risk of being killed per gonotrophic cycle, which in turn can be used to estimate the impact on the vectorial capacity of the local mosquito population, and thus on the intensity of malaria transmission.

Of course, the estimates depend on the assumption that what happens in experimental huts closely resembles what happens in real life when nets are used under routine domestic conditions.

Although experimental huts are intended to approximate the real-life situation as much as possible, they are obviously not perfect: we should not assume that the environmental factors, and the behaviour of humans and mosquitoes, is exactly the same as in ordinary houses. As we have already noted, the entomological effects observed in experimental huts are somewhat variable: they vary between settings, and with factors like net-fabric. Also, these effects can be dose-dependent, fading over time as the insecticide is gradually lost, but with unpredictable and counter-intuitive effects; for example, if reduced irritation/excito-repellency leads to greater exposure, there can be greater mortality with a lower dose (Corbel et al., 2004).

There are also important factors, such as feeding on non-human hosts, that cannot be measured in an experimental hut. The risk of being killed by the insecticide on a net, before or after feeding, presumably depends on a series of probabilities and proportions: the probability that the meal will be taken on a human host, the proportion of humans using an ITN, the probability of picking up a lethal dose of insecticide while trying to get in or out of the ITN, etc.

For example, the local vector may take many of its bloodmeals from non-human hosts.

A blood-seeking female of a highly anthropophilic species, such as *Anopheles gambiae* s.s, presumably faces a much greater risk of contacting an ITN and being killed than a similar female of a more zoophilic species like *An. arabiensis*. In order to estimate the probability that a blood-seeking female will encounter an ITN, we need to know not only the proportion of people sleeping under ITNs, but also the Human Blood Index (HBI), the proportion of bloodmeals taken from humans. Unfortunately, our methods of estimating HBI are inevitably biased, because we still do not know how to take samples of fed females that are representative of the population as a whole (Garrett-Jones and Shidrawi, 1969).

1.3. Early evidence from field trials of ITNs

We have seen that experimental huts allow us to predict what will happen at population level. In this section, we ask whether these predictions are borne out by village-scale epidemiological field trials, looking first at the entomological then the epidemiological evidence.

The first point to note is that we do not have a good entomological measure of personal protection at the population level. Consider a cluster-randomised trial in which there are villages with and without treated nets. We do not have a good way to measure the barrier effect of the nets, that is, the degree to which they isolate net-users from the local mosquitoes. The best we can do is to sample and characterise the mosquito populations in the two types of villages (taking care to consider phenotypic effects on vector behaviour), in order to measure population-level effects on vectorial capacity.

When measuring vector abundance, we have to take care to consider and avoid the effects of induced exophily. There is ample evidence from experimental hut studies that the presence of an occupied treated net in a room can radically alter the behaviour of mosquitoes in that room, driving both fed and unfed females that would normally rest indoors to exit from the room and rest elsewhere.

This best evidence confirming the existence of a community effect of ITNs comes from the early field-trials of the 1980s and early 1990s. The best entomological evidence comes from a small trial in Tanzania (Magesa et al., 1991). In order to avoid the problem of induced exophily, the entomological monitoring in this study was carried in a few selected “sentinel houses” in each village. The occupants of these houses were given untreated nets², throughout the study and in both treated and untreated villages, thereby ensuring the comparability of samples taken in treated and untreated villages. Vectors were caught primarily using CDC light traps hung next to occupied untreated nets; the validity of this method, and its ability to field unbiased samples of blood-seeking females, was confirmed using a smaller number of human-landing catches (Lines et al., 1991). The results indicated that in villages given full coverage with ITNs, there was substantial reduction in vector abundance, and also a reduction in the proportion of these females found to be sporozoite positive. The combination of these two effects produced a substantial degree of protection – 91% to 97% reduction in EIR -- for the minority of people not using ITNs in the treated villages (Curtis et al., 2003, Magesa et al., 1991). In other words, within the treated villages, the intervention reduced exposure to malaria by more than ten-fold, even in people not using nets. People who were using nets presumably enjoyed a substantial additional degree of personal protection. The unique feature of this trial, however, was the use of detailed age-grading¹ using Polovodova’s technique, which classifies females into multiple

² Note that this use of untreated nets is no longer ethical, now that ITN-use is the accepted standard of care.

age-classes, according to the number of dilatations in the ovariole stalk, which corresponds to the number of times they have laid eggs.

Figure 1 shows the data from more than 4000 such dissections, as presented by Magesa et al 1991. We see the results from two villages, before and after the introduction of treated nets. The key points to note are:

- During the baseline period, before any interventions, the decline in numbers among >1-parous females is a remarkably straight-line, on the log-scale. This implies that the proportion surviving from one gonotrophic cycle to the next is more or less constant and independent of age.
- After intervention (filled symbols), in the villages with ITNs (Mn'gaza and Mlingano), there is a clear impact on longevity.
 - There is still a more-or-less linear decline with age, but now the downward slope is substantially steeper. There is more noise in the data, because the numbers are generally smaller, but the increase in slope is very clear.
 - This implies that the proportion surviving each cycle is now much smaller, although it remains largely independent of age.
- Interestingly, a very similar pattern is seen in Mindu, before and after house-spraying with DDT³. This implies that in this study, IRS and ITNs had very similar effects on vector longevity.

³ This study remains, as far as we know, the best available evidence confirming Macdonald's hypothesis that the epidemiological impact of IRS is mediated primarily by a reduction in vector survivorship.

Figure 1: Data of Magesa et al (1991) showing the results of age-grading of mosquitoes from three villages in Tanzania (Mindu, Mlingano and Mng'aza), before and after the introduction of pyrethroid treated nets into Mlingano and Mng'aza, and house-spraying with DDT in Mindu. Each dilatation (in the ovariole stalk) indicates an oviposition event, so that the class with "0 dilatations" are nullipars, the "2 dilatations" class are two-parous, etc. Note the log-scale on the y-axis (numbers of females in age-class). Note that the numbers in the oldest age-classes are very small and subject to sampling error. We see that after first gonotrophic cycle, the decline in numbers from age-class to the next is approximately linear indicating that the proportion surviving each cycle is approximately constant. After intervention with ITNs in Mlingano and Mng'aza, and with DDT in Mindu, the slope of the line is much steeper, indicating reduced survival per-cycle.

Epidemiological evidence for the existence and importance of community-level protection emerged from a series of ITNs trials in which child-mortality (measured by longitudinal demographic surveillance systems) was the primary outcome. In some of these trials – notably those in Ghana and western Kenya – it was observed that epidemiological protection was enjoyed not only by the residents of ITN-treated villages, but also by nearby households without ITNs, up to a distance of a few hundred metres (Binka et al., 1998, Hawley et al., 2003). This clearly confirms that ITNs reduce transmission by population-level effects on vector longevity; moreover, the spatial scale of the observed effects is reassuringly consistent with other studies of mosquito movement (e.g. (Gillies, 1961).

However, one of the same series of child-mortality trials – the National Impregnated Bednet Programme in The Gambia - produced entirely different results. Here, the observed impact on child mortality was similar to that seen elsewhere, but the ento-epidemiological mechanism producing this outcome was apparently very different (D'Alessandro et al., 1995a, Thomson et al., 1995a, Thomson et al., 1995b). There was both entomological and epidemiological evidence that in this setting, community-level protection was either absent or very different from that observed in Tanzania, Ghana and western Kenya.

Previous entomological studies in The Gambia had already observed that the introduction of treated nets led to a major reduction in the density of indoor-resting fed females (Snow et al., 1988). At the time, it was assumed that this implied a reduction in the local mosquito population as a whole. However, in a later study in The Gambia, a series of indoor and outdoor human-landing catches, and indoor-resting catches, were carried out in ten pairs of treated and untreated villages. The results confirmed the previous finding that compared to untreated villages, catches in treated villages showed a major reduction in indoor-resting densities. However, there was no reduction in the abundance of vectors trying to bite human baits; nor was there any evidence for a reduction in the parous rate and sporozoite rate. This suggested that the reduction in indoor-resting vectors was probably a reflection of induced exophily (Quinones et al., 1998). There was little or no evidence for a reduction in the true size of the local vector population. It seemed that non-net-users were exposed to similar entomological inoculation rates, whether or not they lived in a community where most people were using treated nets.

Epidemiological data from The Gambia told a similar story. Living in a treated rather than an untreated village was not associated with any epidemiological protection for non-net users, either in the longitudinal incidence monitoring, or in the cross-sectional parasitaemia surveys (D'Alessandro et al., 1995a, D'Alessandro et al., 1995b). Rather, protection was exclusively associated at the individual level with sleeping under a treated net (Figure 2).

Figure 2: In the Gambian National Impregnated Bednet Programme, in which a 25% reduction in all-cause child mortality was observed, a cross-sectional survey was carried out of children in Primary Health Care (PHC) villages with or without treated nets, and in non-PHC villages; each child was classified as using a treated net (ITN; only in treated PHC villages), using an untreated net (UTN), or using no net. The results suggest that the risk of parasitaemia depends primarily on the child's own net-using status. Children with no net apparently gain little or no protection from living in a treated village.

This could be due to (either or both of) two possible reasons (Quinones et al., 1998). First, it seems possible that the ITNs in this trial – which were treated with a moderate dosage of permethrin, some being made of heavy cotton fabric -- were giving good protection against biting but not killing mosquitoes as much as the nets in the other trials. Second, it could be that in The Gambia, the introduction of ITNs did cause an area-wide reduction in vectorial capacity, but it did so on a larger scale, including both treated and untreated villages. Perhaps, in The Gambia compared to the trial sites in Tanzania, Ghana and western Kenya, the major breeding sites tend to be located further away from villages; in this case, we might expect that the commuting movement of vectors from village to breeding site and back again could mediate to a greater

level of population exchange between neighbouring villages. In other words, it is possible that in the Gambian trial, the ITNs could have been causing substantial amounts of insecticidal mortality, but the beneficial consequences of this mortality – in the form of reduced vector abundance, longevity and sporozoite rates – were shared more or less equally between treated and untreated communities (Thomson et al., 1995b). It remains uncertain which of these two possible explanations was more important in producing this puzzling lack of contrasts between the mosquito populations of treated and untreated villages.

Due to the mobility of vectors, the question always arises during the design of a cluster-randomised trial of ITNs: how big do the clusters have to be? If they are too small, there may be spill-over and contamination between neighbouring clusters that may go undetected. When thinking about this, trial managers often cite the evidence from mark-recapture studies, as summarised for example by Gillies (1988). Such studies typically observe that with anopheline vectors, the observed median flight range between release and recapture is between 1 and 3 kilometres. This is true, but it must also be noted that in these studies, all but a few of these recaptures are actually caught within a few days of release: often within 2 to 5 days, that is 1 or 2 gonotrophic cycles.

We are interested in the epidemiological effects of intervention, and how far these effects may be distributed by mosquito movement. In order to understand this, it is helpful to consider an individual mosquito that is killed by a treated net just before it would have taken an infective bloodmeal. Then consider all the places where this mosquito might have flown if it had not been killed. It would have taken 9-12 days for the infection in that bloodmeal to develop into sporozoites. This raises the question: “Where, if the mosquito had not been killed, would those infective bites have taken place? Who would have been bitten?”. The answer to this question defines the spatial distribution of the people who gained the epidemiological benefit.

This idea of the “flightpath not taken” helps us to understand how, when a mosquito is killed in one location, the epidemiological benefits are distributed around the surrounding area. One key implication is that we have to consider not just how far this imaginary female would have flown in 2-5 days, but how far she would have flown by the time she started to deliver infectious sporozoites in her bites, which could be much longer. So perhaps we should be asking “How far would she typically fly in 8 days?” – which is likely to be much further than 1 to 3 kilometres.

Some general conclusions can be drawn from these early trials. The entomological effects of treated nets suggest that they can give epidemiological protection in two ways:

- Personal protection: occupants of the net are less likely to be bitten by whatever mosquitoes may be outside.
- The community effect: a reduction in the vectorial capacity of the local mosquito population. This can be seen as a reduction in vector longevity and is caused by the fact that blood-seeking females risk being killed whenever they try to seek a meal. The concentration and spatial extent of this effect must depend on local patterns of mosquito dispersal between hosts, which vary between settings as a result of vector bionomics and the characteristics of the intervention deployed.

A priori, and drawing on the experimental hut evidence on the entomological effects of ITNs, we would expect the relative strength of the community effect (as opposed to personal protection) to vary with a number of contextual factors. In general, it will depend on the probability that a female will be killed just before or after a bloodmeal. This can be broken down into series of subordinate probabilities and proportions: the probability that the meal will be taken on a human host, the proportion of humans using an ITN, the probability of picking up a lethal dose of insecticide while trying to get in or out of the ITNs. Hence the magnitude of the community effect is likely to vary between settings, depending on a number contextual factors, such as:

- Zoophily: substantial community-level effects are unlikely in settings where the local vector species is zoophilic, and takes only a small proportion of bloodmeals on humans;
- The fabric and insecticidal dosage of the ITN;
- Genes for insecticide resistance in the vector;
- The relative accessibility of humans and non-human animal hosts as potential bloodmeal hosts.

Therefore, we should remain open to the idea that community-level effects are expected to vary between settings, and they could even be conspicuous in some settings but undetectable in others.

Most epidemiological field-trials of ITNs are designed for per-protocol epidemiological analysis and, with only basic entomological monitoring, such trials are perfectly adequate for measuring overall effectiveness, but additional measurements are needed in order to differentiate personal protection from population-level (community) effects. A number of field trials of ITNs have been conducted since the early mortality studies. To evaluate the evidence collectively available from these trials towards understanding the community effect of ITNs, we conducted a systematic review of the literature.

SECTION 2. Evidence for the Community Effect from ITN Trials: a Systematic Review

2.1 Methods

The original Cochrane review of the effectiveness of ITNs for preventing malaria (Lengeler, 2004) was recently updated by Pryce et al to identify any new studies and to explore whether the evidence from trials conducted before pyrethroid resistance became widespread can be applied to estimate the impact of ITNs on malaria transmission today (Pryce et al., 2018). The review included individual randomised controlled trials (RCTs) and cluster RCTs (cRCTs) comparing insecticide-treated nets or curtains with no nets or untreated nets. A total of 23 trials met their inclusion criteria.

Studies following a randomised controlled trial design were included if the intervention group received nets treated with a synthetic pyrethroid and the control group was either untreated nets or no nets. Studies where the control group received indoor residual spraying, or nets treated with new insecticide formulations or combinations were excluded. Insecticide-treated curtain studies were excluded as these were not deemed relevant to the current focus on large-scale ITN distribution for vector control. All non-randomised studies were excluded. Similarly, studies which reported on entomological outcomes without any epidemiological outcomes were also excluded. The contribution of purely entomological studies and studies with alternative study designs to the discourse on community effect are considered elsewhere in this paper.

We used the search results of the Cochrane review by Pryce et al to explore what evidence is available from randomised clinical trials towards understanding the contributions of personal protection and community-level effects towards effectiveness of ITNs in different settings. We replicated the search strategy of Pryce et al but included date limits of 19 April 2018 to 10 July 2020 to identify any additional relevant clinical trials published since their review. Reference lists of included studies were checked for additional papers of relevance to our review question and the following reviews were also consulted: (Choi et al., 2019, Gleave et al., 2018, Strode et al., 2014, Yang et al., 2018).

Data on the trial setting and design, and epidemiological and entomological outcome data were extracted from included studies. Data on the trial setting included main vector species, level of malaria transmission, and any reported insecticide resistance. All published articles relating to the included studies were reviewed for relevant information and authors contacted for additional information if a publication could not be located. Epidemiological outcome data were extracted by intervention versus control arm on mortality, clinical malaria, severe malaria, parasite prevalence, and anaemia, as available. Risk of bias of included

studies was assessed based on guidelines in the Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews (Higgins JPT et al., 2019). In summary, the risk was classified as 'low', 'some concerns', or 'high' for each study for each of the following types of bias: selection bias (random sequence generation; allocation concealment), performance bias (blinding of participants and personnel), detection bias (blinding outcome assessment for self-reported fever; blinding outcome assessment for all other outcomes), attrition bias (incomplete outcome data), reporting bias (selective reporting), and baseline imbalance. An overall judgement of bias was then made for each study: 'low risk' where the trial was judged to be at low risk of bias for all domains, or if there were some concerns in one of the domains, these were not judged to be reason to consider the trial at some concern overall (for example, although the randomisation process was not described, intervention and control groups were similar at baseline); 'some concerns' where the trial was judged to raise some concerns in two or more domains, but not to be at high risk of bias for any domain; 'high risk' where the trial was judged to be at high risk of bias in at least one domain, or the trial was judged to have some concerns for multiple domains in a way that substantially lowered confidence in the result.

Where studies conducted entomological data collection alongside the trial, the outcomes of vector abundance (density, human biting rate), sporozoite rate, and annual entomological inoculation rate (EIR) were also extracted by intervention versus control arm, as available. Data on the selection of vector sampling sites and vector collection methods were extracted from studies reporting entomological outcomes to be able to judge whether sampling bias was present.

The nature of the data available and the question being addressed by this review did not support the use of meta-analysis to pool results in to a single outcome measure of community effect. We therefore took the synthesis without meta-analysis (SWiM) approach recommended by Cochrane (Campbell et al., 2020, McKenzie JE and Brennan SE, 2019). We used the previously described ento-epidemiological mechanism theory for how ITNs could achieve a community effect on malaria transmission to explore and describe the extracted epidemiological and entomological data from all included studies. Studies that presented epidemiological or entomological outcomes in such a way to provide direct evidence of a community effect of ITNs were included in the detailed synthesis.

The evidence for personal protection versus community effect that can be determined from clinical outcomes depends on study design and/or analysis. Epidemiological outcomes reported by individually-randomised studies can only measure personal protection from ITN use. Epidemiological outcomes from per protocol analysis of cluster RCTs (cRCT) i.e. differences in outcomes between intervention or control clusters, provide a measure of personal protection combined with any community effect that may exist. In order to

separate personal and community effects, the epidemiological outcomes from a cRCT should be reported separately for users and non-users in intervention and control clusters. Alternatively, spatial analysis of epidemiological outcomes amongst non-users by proximity to ITN users or intervention clusters can also explore whether a community effect is in evidence. Epidemiological outcomes were disaggregated by users/non-users with or without spatial analysis where reported by the study authors. These studies were included in the data synthesis.

These epidemiological manifestations of the community effect reflect the fact that a proportion of vectors are killed by insecticide every time they try to feed. In cluster-RCTs, we expect the local mosquito populations in intervention villages (compared to those in control villages) to have reduced abundance, parous rates and sporozoite rates (Curtis et al., 2003, Magesa et al., 1991). The magnitude of these reductions presumably depends on the proportion killed in every gonotrophic cycle, which in turn depends on contextual factors including ITN coverage and the host-preferences of the vector (see section 1.3 and discussion). These comparisons are fairly straightforward in the case of sporozoite rates and parous rates. For measuring an effect on abundance, it is important not to rely on counts of indoor-resting females, as these are sensitive to bias by insecticide-induced exophily (Quinones et al., 1998). Human-landing catches are the ideal sampling method for this purpose. It is useful to check for consistency between different entomological indicators. Theoretically, if sample sizes are adequate, we would expect sporozoite rates to be the most sensitive indicator. Thus, if a community effect is really present, it would not be surprising to observe, in treated villages, a significant reduction in sporozoite rates, and a more modest and perhaps not statistically significant reduction in vector densities. On the other hand, in studies reporting a reduction in densities but not in sporozoite rates, it is important to consider the possibility that the apparent reduction in densities is due to induced exophily, and would not be seen in human landing catches.

In the synthesis of data from the studies identified as providing direct evidence for the review question, we explored patterns in the data, and investigated similarities and differences between the findings of different studies. Vote counting was used to summarise the epidemiological and entomological evidence for or against a community effect based on the direction of the effect; magnitude and statistical significance of the effect were not considered (McKenzie JE and Brennan SE, 2019). The five constructs of the GRADE (Grading of Recommendation, Assessment, Development and Evaluation) framework to assess certainty of evidence were applied, following the guidance of Murad et al for reviews without a single estimate of effect (Murad et al., 2017). These five constructs are (i) *risk of bias*, due to methodological limitations; (ii) *indirectness*, a judgement on how dissimilar the research evidence is to the clinical question under review; (iii) *imprecision*, considering sample sizes and width of 95% CI around effect measures; (iv) *inconsistency*, in the direction and

magnitude of effect across studies; and (v) *likelihood of publication bias*. Reasons for heterogeneity were explored through consideration of the contextual factors that could have influenced the results. These factors were informed by our ento-epidemiological theory; specifically: malaria transmission intensity, degree of anthropophily, insecticide resistance and level of ITN use, and the size and distribution of clusters.

2.2 Results

2.2.1 Overview of included studies

Of the 23 studies included in the Cochrane review by Pryce et al, two were excluded from our review as the intervention being evaluated was insecticide-treated curtains (Habluetzel et al., 1997, Rabarison et al., 1995). No additional eligible studies were found that had been published since the review by Pryce et al. However, an additional six papers related to the 21 trials were found that did not contribute to the Cochrane review but that provided data of relevance to the community effect question (Binka et al., 1998, D'Alessandro et al., 1995b, Gimnig et al., 2003a, Gimnig et al., 2003b, Howard et al., 2000, Smithuis et al., 2013b).

In total, 31 papers on 21 studies contributed data to the research question. Ten of these studies were conducted in sub-Saharan Africa (Cameroon, Cote d'Ivoire, Ghana, two in The Gambia, three in Kenya, Sierra Leone, and Tanzania), five in Asia (Cambodia, Myanmar, Pakistan, Thailand, and the Thai-Burmese border), and six in South America (Colombia, Ecuador, Nicaragua, two in Peru, and Venezuela). The control group for eleven of the studies had no nets; for the other ten studies the control group had untreated nets.

2.2.2 Epidemiological evidence addressing the community effect

Of the 21 studies considered in this review, five were individually-randomised and so could only provide evidence on the personal protection offered by ITNs, and sixteen reported per protocol analyses of a cRCT, providing evidence on the combined personal and community effects of ITNs. Four of the sixteen cRCTs also reported epidemiological outcomes in such a way that personal and community effects of ITN use could be separated (Table 1).

Findings from the individually-randomised trials demonstrated significant personal protection of ITNs against clinical falciparum malaria amongst migrant workers in Thailand (Kamol-Ratanakul and Prasittisuk, 1992), refugee camps in Pakistan (Rowland et al., 1996), schoolchildren on the Thai-Burmese border (Luxemburger

et al., 1994) and children under five years in western Kenya (Sexton et al., 1990); significant reductions in *P. falciparum* parasite prevalence were also found in Tanzania and Pakistan (Rowland et al., 1996, Fraser-Hurt et al., 1999). The protective efficacy was mixed with respect to vivax malaria and anaemia: a significant reduction in clinical vivax malaria was found in Pakistan refugee camps (Rowland et al., 1996), but there was no effect on vivax parasitaemia or clinical vivax malaria in schoolchildren on the Thai-Burmese border (Luxemburger et al., 1994); ITN users showed a significant increase in haemoglobin levels in Tanzania (Fraser-Hurt et al., 1999), but not in Pakistan (Rowland et al., 1996). The risk of bias in the individually-randomised trials was generally low risk (Kamol-Ratanakul and Prasittisuk, 1992, Luxemburger et al., 1994) or presenting some concerns related to lack of detail of the randomisation process and loss to follow-up (Rowland et al., 1996) or lack of similarity of baseline characteristics (Sexton et al., 1990). One of the studies was judged to be at high risk of bias due to lack of detail on the randomisation process and imbalance in baseline parasite prevalence (Fraser-Hurt et al., 1999) (Table 2).

The per protocol analyses of the sixteen cRCTs show the overall effectiveness (i.e. combined personal and community effect) of ITNs on preventing malaria. These effects are described in detail in Pryce et al, including meta-analyses where appropriate (Pryce et al., 2018). In summary: four of the cRCTs were powered to measure all-cause child mortality as an outcome, all of which found a significant protective efficacy; this ranged from 16% in Ghana and 17% western Kenya to 25% in The Gambia, and 33% in coastal Kenya (Binka et al., 1996, D'Alessandro et al., 1995a, Nevill et al., 1996, Phillips-Howard et al., 2003). All four of these trials were judged to be at low risk of bias. Twelve cRCT studies measured clinical malaria, nine of these demonstrated a significant reduction across a range of transmission settings in sub-Saharan Africa and South America, and three (Ecuador, Myanmar and Cambodia (Kroeger et al., 1995, Smithuis et al., 2013a, Sochantha et al., 2006)) did not find significant differences between intervention and control clusters (Table 1). Eight studies measured parasite prevalence and six measured anaemia. As with the individually-randomised studies, the impact on these outcomes was mixed with half of the cRCTs that measured these outcomes reporting significant protection against parasite prevalence (in Cameroon, Cote d'Ivoire, Kenya, and Venezuela (Moyou-Somo et al., 1995, Henry et al., 2005, Phillips-Howard et al., 2003, Magris et al., 2007)) or anaemia (in Cote d'Ivoire, The Gambia, and Kenya) (Henry et al., 2005, Snow et al., 1988, Phillips-Howard et al., 2003), and the other half finding no evidence of protection of ITNs (parasite prevalence: one study in Cambodia, two studies in The Gambia, and one study in Myanmar (Sochantha et al., 2006, Snow et al., 1988, D'Alessandro et al., 1995a, Smithuis et al., 2013a); anaemia: Myanmar, Sierra Leone, and Venezuela (Smithuis et al., 2013a, Marbiah et al., 1998, Magris et al., 2007)). The risk of bias judgement for six of the twelve studies reporting morbidity outcomes was high risk due to lack of blinding or parasitological confirmation of self-reported fever as the primary outcome and lack of detail on the randomisation process

(in Cote d'Ivoire, Colombia, Ecuador, two sites in Peru, and Nicaragua (Henry et al., 2005, Kroeger et al., 1995, Kroeger et al., 1999)). Two of the studies had some concerns of bias due to lack of detail on the randomisation process and baseline comparison (Cameroon (Moyou-Somo et al., 1995)), or lack of detail on missing data by arm (Venezuela (Magris et al., 2007)). The remaining four studies had low risk of bias (Cambodia, The Gambia, Myanmar, and Sierra Leone (Sochantha et al., 2006, Snow et al., 1988, Smithuis et al., 2013a, Marbiah et al., 1998)).

The four studies which present their data in such a way to separate the personal protection from the community effect of ITNs are the early mortality trial by D'Alessandro in The Gambia (D'Alessandro et al., 1995a, D'Alessandro et al., 1995b) and three of the four large mortality trials that followed: Ghana (Binka et al., 1998, Binka et al., 1996), coastal Kenya (Howard et al., 2000, Nevill et al., 1996) and western Kenya (Hawley et al., 2003, Phillips-Howard et al., 2003, ter Kuile et al., 2003). The risk of bias in the mortality outcomes for all four of these studies was low. However, there was a high risk of bias for the morbidity analysis conducted as a part of the western Kenya study due to incomplete outcome data; only children aged less than 36 months were sampled for the morbidity analysis (ter Kuile et al., 2003), compared to the study population of 1-59 month-old children for the mortality trial (Phillips-Howard et al., 2003).

The trial in The Gambia demonstrated significant personal protection of ITNs with a 25% protective efficacy against mortality in children aged 1-9 years (D'Alessandro et al., 1995a). However, there was no impact on parasite prevalence between intervention and control arms. Further analysis of cross-sectional parasite prevalence data, seems to show that prevalence was more dependent on a child's own net use (ITN, UTN or no net) than whether they lived in an intervention or control village (D'Alessandro et al., 1995b). This supports the importance of personal protection over community effect in this setting.

In contrast, spatial analyses of mortality amongst non-users according to their proximity to households of ITN-users in Ghana, the Kenyan coast, and western Kenya found evidence of a community effect. In Ghana, the per protocol analysis (i.e. comparison of intervention versus control arms) found that ITNs offered a 17% protective efficacy against mortality for children under five (Binka et al., 1996). The death rate amongst non-users (in control households) increased with distance from the nearest households with ITNs ($p=0.007$). The model suggested that a shift of 100m away from the boundary was associated with an increase in risk of individuals without ITNs of 6.7%, indicating that ITNs were protecting other individuals without ITNs who sleep close to protected households (Binka et al., 1998). In the coastal Kenya study, a 44% reduction in severe malaria hospital admissions was found between intervention and control clusters (Nevill et al., 1996). The reduced incidence of severe malaria was the same for users and non-users in the intervention clusters.

In addition, for children not using ITNs, increasing ITN use in the surrounding area was associated with a decreasing risk of severe malaria; the effect was significant for areas up to 1.5km away (Howard et al., 2000). In western Kenya, ITNs prevented approximately one in four infant deaths and significantly reduced malaria-associated morbidity (Phillips-Howard et al., 2003). A protective effect of ITNs against child mortality, moderate anaemia, high-density parasitaemia, and anaemia was found for households without ITNs located within 300m of intervention households. The authors found that this community effect on nearby households without ITNs was approximately as strong as the effect within villages with ITNs, however, the strength of community effect depended on at least moderate coverage with ITNs in neighbouring households (>50%) (Hawley et al., 2003).

2.2.3 Entomological evidence addressing the community effect

Fourteen of the 21 included studies reported that entomological data was collected alongside the trial; the remaining seven did not conduct any entomological investigations (Table 3). Of the fourteen studies where entomology was conducted, seven did not have a published entomology paper or include sufficient detail in the trial paper on the entomological methods and outcomes to extract data relevant for the community effect question (Henry et al., 2005, Kroeger et al., 1999, Kroeger et al., 1995, Binka et al., 1996, Moyou-Somo et al., 1995).

Of the seven studies that reported entomological outcomes, five had data suitable to assess whether there was a community effect or not, namely a measure of vector abundance, sporozoite rate and entomological inoculation rate. These studies were two from The Gambia ((Thomson et al., 1995a, Thomson et al., 1995b) and (Lindsay et al., 1989)), and one each from Sierra Leone (Magbity et al., 1997), coastal Kenya (Mbogo et al., 1996), and western Kenya (Gimnig et al., 2003a, Gimnig et al., 2003b) The remaining two entomological studies could not assess community effect due to too few sporozoite-positive mosquitoes (Kenya (Sexton et al., 1990); Myanmar (Smithuis et al., 2013b)).

The entomological study by Lindsay *et al* that accompanied the 1987 trial of permethrin-treated nets in The Gambia (Snow et al., 1988) measured a large reduction in indoor resting densities and an estimated 90% reduction in human-biting rates which translated to a reduction in seasonal EIR (Lindsay et al., 1989). However, whilst this may suggest a community effect in reduction of vector abundance, the use of indoor resting catches and exit traps as the only methods of mosquito capture bias the interpretation; these methods do not fully capture all exiting mosquitoes which will be higher in treated households due to the excito-repellency effect of ITNs, potentially producing a false positive for a community effect (Quinones et al., 1998). A significant reduction in sporozoite rate would be a stronger indication of a community effect on

transmission, however, this was not found despite large numbers of anophelines examined. The entomological study by Thomson *et al*, also in The Gambia, that accompanied the D'Alessandro mortality trial collected mosquitoes in sentinel houses of paired intervention and control villages representing three of the five distinct ecological areas identified prior to the trial (Thomson et al., 1995a). Indoor resting densities of *An. gambiae* s.l. were significantly lower in intervention villages compared to their paired control; there was no significant difference in density of exiting vectors. Again, the excito-repellency bias limits the conclusions that can be drawn from these data. Outdoor human bait catches also conducted in two of the three village pairs found no significant difference in outdoor biting. Only mosquitoes caught by indoor spray catches and exit traps were included in the calculations of sporozoite rate and EIR, neither of which demonstrated significant differences between intervention and control village pairs. The authors observe that one village showed evidence for a community effect (significantly reduced outdoor biting compared to its paired control, which was not seen in other intervention villages). However, this village had very high ITN use and was geographically isolated which was not considered to be representative of intervention villages overall (Thomson et al., 1995a). On the whole, these data do not support the presence of a community effect of ITNs in this trial in The Gambia, the conclusion also drawn by the study authors given the interspersed nature of intervention and control villages and the high levels of movement of mosquitoes between neighbouring villages (Thomson et al., 1995b).

The entomology conducted by Mbogo et al in coastal Kenya presented mixed results that make the assessment of a community effect inconclusive (Mbogo et al., 1996). Indoor and outdoor human biting rates were consistently higher in the intervention areas compared to control areas before and after the intervention was introduced. A greater decrease in indoor vector abundance was measured in intervention versus control areas, however, similar changes in human biting rate and sporozoite rate were seen in intervention and control areas. The relatively small numbers of mosquitoes captured indoors for sporozoite testing, particularly in the intervention areas, means it is possible that the lack of any significant changes was a result of insufficient power rather than true absence of a community effect.

In contrast, the entomological study conducted in western Kenya (Gimnig et al., 2003a, Gimnig et al., 2003b) did provide evidence for a community effect of ITNs. Although there were significant reductions in vector abundance in intervention versus control sites, these results suffer from induced excito-repellency bias as indoor resting catches and exit traps were the only methods of mosquito collection (Gimnig et al., 2003a, Gimnig et al., 2003b). However, in contrast to the Gambian entomological studies, significant reductions in sporozoite rate (and EIR) for *An. gambiae* s.l. were found in intervention areas compared to control areas (0.8% versus 3.4%, $p=0.026$), supporting a community effect on transmission. In western Kenya, the

entomological data supports the strong epidemiological evidence for a community effect on malaria (Hawley et al., 2003). Entomological evidence for a community effect was also reported in Sierra Leone (Magbity et al., 1997). A greater array of mosquito collection methods was used by Magbity et al, avoiding the risk of bias due to excito-repellency seen in studies only using indoor resting catches and exit traps. Vector density and human-biting rates as measured by outdoor human bait catches and indoor CDC light traps, as well as indoor resting catches and exit traps, were not significantly reduced between intervention and control villages. However, (with the exception of one outlier village) there were significant reductions in sporozoite rates, providing support for a community-level effect on malaria transmission.

2.3 Data synthesis

2.3.1 What is the evidence for a community effect?

In summary, six of the 21 studies included in this review reported results in a way suitable to assess community effect separately to personal protection (Table 4). Four of these six studies provided evidence for a community effect of ITNs: in Ghana, coastal Kenya and western Kenya, evidence for a community effect was supported by epidemiological outcomes (Binka et al., 1998, Hawley et al., 2003, Howard et al., 2000). In western Kenya, entomological evidence also supported the presence of a community effect (Gimnig et al., 2003a, Gimnig et al., 2003b); in coastal Kenya the entomological data was inconclusive (Mbogo et al., 1996), and in Ghana entomological data were not reported. The evidence for a community effect in Sierra Leone came from entomological data (Magbity et al., 1997); epidemiological data were not presented in a way to separate community effect from personal protection (Marbiah et al., 1998). Two of the six studies did not provide evidence for a community effect of ITNs; both of these studies were conducted in The Gambia, representing the varied ecological settings found in the country. Epidemiological and entomological outcomes reported by D'Alessandro et al support the importance of personal protection over community effect in this setting (D'Alessandro et al., 1995b, Thomson et al., 1995a, Thomson et al., 1995b); in the trial by Snow et al, the epidemiological data were not presented in a way to separate community effect from personal protection (Snow et al., 1988), but the entomological data do not support a community effect (Lindsay et al., 1989).

2.3.2 What is the level of certainty in that evidence?

Summarising the community effect into a single outcome was not possible based on the studies contributing to data synthesis in this review. For example, some studies provided either epidemiological or entomological

analysis to separate community effect from personal protection, whilst others provided both. The method or outcome that was used to assess community effect further varied – D’Alessandro et al explored differences in parasite prevalence between ITN-users and non-users in intervention and control villages in The Gambia, in coastal Kenya difference in severe admissions between ITN-users and non-users was compared, whereas in Ghana and western Kenya spatial analysis was used to explore differences in malaria mortality or morbidity (respectively) for children living in control clusters according to their distance from intervention households (Table 5).

Therefore, we cannot produce a summary measure for the size of community effect with a plausible confidence interval given the variation in outcome data. However, it is still possible to judge the certainty of evidence according to the GRADE criteria (Table 6).

Risk of bias

For all of the four studies contributing epidemiological data, risk of bias was low, suggesting we can be confident in the direction of epidemiological evidence for (Ghana, coastal Kenya, western Kenya) or against (The Gambia) a community effect.

For the five studies contributing entomological data, one of the studies had a low risk of bias of induced exophily and low risk of sampling bias due to the selection of vector sampling sites (Sierra Leone, which found evidence for a community effect in the significant lower sporozoite rates in intervention sites compared to control sites (Magbity et al., 1997)). The vector sampling methods used by three of the other five studies (two in The Gambia and one in western Kenya (Thomson et al., 1995a, Thomson et al., 1995b, Lindsay et al., 1989, Gimnig et al., 2003b)) relied on indoor resting catches and exit traps; therefore reported reductions in abundance of indoor resting mosquitoes are at risk of bias due to induced exophily and cannot be taken on their own as evidence for a community effect. In western Kenya, sporozoite rates and EIR were significantly lower in intervention compared to control sites, supporting a community effect on transmission (Gimnig et al., 2003b). In contrast, lack of significant changes in the sporozoite rate and EIR in the two Gambian studies does not support the presence of a community effect in this setting (although it should be noted that in the study by Lindsay et al, the number of sporozoite-positive mosquitoes was very small (12/2142) which limits the power to detect differences between intervention and control areas (Lindsay et al., 1989)). A fourth study (coastal Kenya) conducted outdoor human landing catches but only in a very small sub-set of clusters and the small numbers of mosquitoes captured (particularly inside intervention households (4/82)) mean it is possible that the lack of any significant change in sporozoite rate was a result of insufficient power rather than true absence of a community effect; the entomological evidence from this

study is therefore inconclusive (Mbogo et al., 1996). Overall, we can have reasonable confidence in the direction of the entomological evidence for (Sierra Leone, western Kenya) or against (The Gambia) the community effect from three of the five studies considered; we are not confident in the direction of entomological effect from the remaining two studies (The Gambia, coastal Kenya).

Given the confidence in the epidemiological evidence for a community effect in coastal Kenya due to low risk of bias, we agree with the study authors' conclusion that ITNs in this setting provided some degree of community effect (Howard et al., 2000). Therefore, taking the epidemiological and entomological evidence together, evidence for a community effect was present in four settings (Ghana, coastal Kenya, western Kenya, Sierra Leone) and absent in two studies from the same setting (The Gambia).

Indirectness

The intervention, comparators and analyses in the studies included in the data synthesis all provide direct evidence to separate the community effect of ITNs from personal protection. Therefore we have no concerns about an influence of indirectness of outcome measures in lowering the certainty of the evidence.

Imprecision

All studies included in the data synthesis were cRCTs with large sample sizes powered to detect changes in all-cause child mortality between intervention and control arms. There was a total of 477 clusters across the four studies contributing epidemiological outcomes. Precision of clinical outcomes therefore not a concern, including disaggregating data e.g. for spatial analysis.

The scale of data collection varied across the five studies contributing entomological data in terms of number of sites and frequency of data collection. A total of 22,861 mosquitoes were examined for sporozoites across four of the five studies that reported this measure (ranging from 729 in coastal Kenya to 13,030 in The Gambia; western Kenya reported percentages only) with a total of 391 positive (ranging from 12 in The Gambia study by Lindsay et al to 191 in Sierra Leone). Low numbers of sporozoite positive mosquitoes can result in low power to detect a difference between intervention and control areas. This may be the case for two of the five entomology studies (coastal Kenya (Mbogo et al., 1996), The Gambia (Lindsay et al., 1989)) where a p-value >0.05 may be due to a lack of power. Overall, imprecision was judged to not be a cause of uncertainty for epidemiological outcomes but of moderate concern for some of the entomological outcomes.

Inconsistency

Overall, four of the six studies reported presence of epidemiological and/or entomological evidence for a community effect. Evidence of a community effect was absent for two studies from The Gambia. However, given the underlying ento-epidemiological theory for how ITNs work, the variation in evidence of community effect is neither unexpected or a cause for concern regarding the certainty of evidence. The contexts of the studies in terms of transmission intensity, vector behaviour, ITN use, spatial distribution of intervention and control clusters and insecticide resistance will all influence the size of community effect. The influence of contextual factors on community effect is considered in further detail below.

Publication bias

We did not strongly suspect publication bias because studies with both positive and negative findings regarding the presence of a community effect were published, and the search for studies was comprehensive to capture the evidence from randomised trials of ITN efficacy. We know of studies with non-randomised designs investigating the presence of community effect of ITNs (e.g. (Escamilla et al., 2017, Klinkenberg et al., 2010, Komazawa et al., 2012)), however these were not included in this review due to the lower certainty of evidence such studies contribute.

Other factors raising the certainty of evidence

Three of the six studies included in the data synthesis had both epidemiological and entomological outcomes suitable to assess evidence of a community effect. In the case of western Kenya, evidence for a community effect was present in both types of outcome; in the Gambia, evidence for a community effect was absent in both; in coastal Kenya strong epidemiological evidence was present but methodological limitations make the entomological evidence inconclusive. Of the other three studies, one reported only epidemiological outcomes and two reported only entomological outcomes relevant to the community effect question.

Three studies reported evidence for a dose response gradient between decreasing proximity of ITN non-users to ITN users and decreased community effect (Binka et al., 1998, Hawley et al., 2003, Howard et al., 2000); two of these studies also reported evidence for a dose response between increasing ITN use and increased community effect (Hawley et al., 2003, Howard et al., 2000). Both of these aspects are discussed further in the following section.

On balance, judging across all of the GRADE domains and considering the epidemiological and entomological evidence base as a whole, we are confident that the certainty of evidence from the six studies in the data synthesis is high.

2.3.3 How do contextual factors influence the community effect?

Differences in the findings of the six studies included in the data synthesis support the importance of contextual factors on the likely strength of community effect. As previously discussed, the lack of a standard single outcome measure for community effect across the studies makes interpretation of heterogeneity challenging. However, we consider in turn the contextual factors identified by the ento-epidemiological theory for ITN effectiveness and how these may be expected to influence the community effect.

Malaria transmission intensity and seasonality varied across the included studies, ranging from moderate seasonal transmission in The Gambia (EIR: 1-24) and coastal Kenya (EIR: 10-30) and moderate perennial in Sierra Leone (EIR: 21-35) to intense seasonal transmission in Ghana (EIR: 100-1000) and intense perennial transmission in western Kenya (EIR: 60-300). This may provide some explanation for the lower relative protective efficacy of ITNs against mortality in Ghana (17%) and western Kenya (16%) compared to The Gambia (25%) and coastal Kenya (33%) – even with the same relative reduction in transmission due to ITN use, the population will still be exposed to high numbers of infectious bites.

ITN use in intervention clusters was around 70% or above across all studies (and in some cases as high as 80% or 90%). However, this may mask variation as reported for The Gambia where ITN use ranged from 56% to 94%, depending on study area (D'Alessandro et al., 1995a). In western Kenya, the authors found that the strength of community effect (i.e. protection against mortality and morbidity outcomes for people in control clusters) depended on at least moderate (>50%) ITN use in the neighbouring intervention cluster (Hawley et al., 2003). Similarly, Howard et al found that for ITN non-users, an increasing level of ITN use in the surrounding area was associated with decreased risk of malaria (Howard et al., 2000).

In terms of heterogeneity, a particular question of interest is 'What is so different about The Gambia that means a community effect was not evident in this setting?'. This can't be explained by the vector's level of anthropophily as the main vector in all six of the studies at the time of data collection was *An. gambiae*, a highly anthropophilic vector. Similarly, there was no evidence of insecticide resistance found (the same is true of all the studies). It is possible that the net material influenced the killing effect of the insecticide as the intervention in The Gambia was to re-treat people's existing nets, some of which will have been cotton rather than synthetic (compared to the other trials which distributed and re-treated nylon or polyester nets). Another reason offered by the authors is that treated and untreated villages were interspersed and vectors were able to move between them which would mask any potential community effect on malaria transmission (Thomson et al., 1995b). The distance between intervention and control villages in The Gambia

varied between 1-5 km and the authors noted that evidence for a community effect was only seen in one village “with very high net use and isolated from nearby villages” (Thomson et al., 1995a). Additional entomological studies in The Gambia by Quinones et al confirmed the lack of effect of ITNs on vector longevity or sporozoite rates in intervention areas compared to control areas (Quinones et al., 1998). The authors propose that the location of most breeding sites outside villages could contribute to the high level of movement of vectors between villages in this setting (Quinones et al., 1998, Thomson et al., 1995b).

Although details on physical size of clusters and distance was not generally reported, a spatial element to study findings was discussed by authors of other included studies. For example, Mbogo et al suggested that the inconclusive entomological evidence for a community effect in coastal Kenya may have been due to movement of vectors between intervention and control areas (Mbogo et al., 1996). The epidemiological analysis from the same trial found that increasing ITN use in the surrounding area was associated with a decreasing risk of severe malaria and that the effect was significant for areas up to 1.5km away (Howard et al., 2000). In western Kenya, Gimnig et al found a protective effect of ITNs on households without ITNs located within 300m of households with ITNs (Hawley et al., 2003). In Ghana, each increase of 100m from an intervention cluster was associated with a 6.7% increase in mortality risk for children in control clusters (Binka et al., 1998). These spatial analyses suggest that the interplay of the size of intervention and control clusters, the distance of separation between them and likely mosquito movement is an important influence on whether evidence for a community effect is found.

SECTION 3. The Expected Effects of ITN Coverage on Malaria Transmission

As we have seen, the community effect of ITNs has many similarities with IRS, in its ento-epidemiological mode of action. IRS is traditionally regarded by vector control professionals as an intervention that must be done well – i.e. with high levels of coverage and with the right dosage of insecticide – in order to work properly because there is no personal protection and IRS relies on a community effect. The conventional recommendation from WHO in the 1960s and 1970s was that at least 80% of target houses should be sprayed: this was the minimum acceptable level of coverage. However, the evidence underlying this recommendation is now obscure (World Health Organisation, 2015). Nevertheless, a recent study by Rehman et al (2011), using data from Malawi and Equatorial Guinea, did produce evidence supporting 80% as an appropriate threshold for IRS, and confirming that lower coverage levels were not associated with statistically significant levels of protection (Rehman et al., 2011).

So does the same apply to ITNs? Since the beginning, we have talked about the community effect of ITNs being associated with “high levels of coverage”, but how high is necessary? We often talk as though there is a threshold. The Abuja targets talked of 60% coverage. At present the notion pertains that universal coverage (presumably meaning 100%) is needed to achieve the optimal impact through ITN deployment; sometimes “80% coverage” is mentioned as a target, but is that correct?

To address this question, we followed the modelling approach first explored by Killeen (Killeen et al., 2007), and by Chitnis (Chitnis et al., 2008), and also using the Swiss TPH model of human malaria infection *Openmalaria*.

Figure 3: Schematic of the model of the mosquito feeding cycle. Reproduced from Chitnis et al. (2012) (Chitnis et al., 2012)

The key parameter for this question is the probability that a female will be killed by an ITN when she seeks a bloodmeal. This probability depends in turn upon (a) the proportion of females seeking a meal from a human rather than an animal host (anthropophily), (b) the proportion of people sleeping under an ITN (coverage), and (c) the probability that the female will be killed by an ITN when trying to feed on its occupant.

For vector control purposes, we are interested in the effect of increasing ITN coverage on vectorial capacity and the entomological inoculation rate (EIR). To illustrate this, we assume a high-transmission situation where the baseline, with zero ITN coverage, is 100 infectious bites per person per year. In order to focus on

the mosquito side of transmission, we start with the assumption that the human side, especially human infectiousness to mosquitoes, is fixed. In effect, this assumption means that we are asking about the short term (immediate) effects of increasing coverage on parasite transmission from mosquito to human, before these have had time to feedback to the dynamics of the parasite in humans. For the same reason, we do not, in this paper, consider how such changes in vectorial capacity will feed through into epidemiological outcomes, either in the short term, or in the long term when equilibrium has been re-established between exposure and immunity.

We prefer this approach, because the epidemiological effect of a halving (50% reduction) in EIR is expected to be very different depending on whether the starting point is high (500 infectious bites per year) or low (<1 infectious bites per year) (Molineaux, 1988). Immunity works to reduce the probability that any one infectious bite will lead to life-threatening disease. Therefore, when transmission is low and the human population has low levels of immunity, we expect a given reduction in EIR to have a relatively direct and obvious effect on epidemiological outcomes. Conversely, when transmission is very intense and the human population has a relatively high degree of immunity, epidemiological outcomes will tend to be less sensitive to a two-fold shift in EIR. However, the immunological mechanisms that modulate epidemiological outcomes are complex, and have a highly non-linear relationship with EIR. These complexities are also important, but they are beyond the scope of this paper, which is focussed on the entomological mechanisms.

The model output in Figure 3 (a, b, c, and d) depicts the expected relationship between EIR and ITN coverage, with a highly anthropophilic vector in an area where nets are deployed. The left-hand panel shows the EIR for ITN-users and non-users in the area separately, the right-hand panel shows the overall mean EIR for both groups combined. In the left hand panel we see that the EIR for ITN-users is slightly less than half that of non-users, over all levels of coverage. In other words, the model assumes that the personal protection effect of the ITN is to reduce the probability of being bitten by a bit more than half. This is considerably lower than the levels of personal protection seen in experimental huts with freshly-treated nets. However, older nets with more holes and less insecticide give far lower levels of personal protection; the value assumed here is intended to represent the mean level of personal protection over the life of the net. Using this model, we see that increasing ITN coverage causes an approximately exponential decline in EIR (Figure 3, a & b).

For the same reason, we consider it *a priori* appropriate to use a log-scale for estimates of EIR, especially when we consider the whole population (ITN-users and non-users combined) (Figure 3 c & d). On a log

scale, we see that the decline with coverage in combined-population EIR is more or less linear, and that in the range of coverage between 15% and 85%, **adding a further 20% of coverage results in a further halving of transmission.** This might be a useful rule-of-thumb to estimate the impact of a specific coverage level achieved by a national programme within a given geographical area. It emphasises that community-level benefits start even at low coverage levels (there is no necessary minimum) but additional coverage is always effective at giving further reductions in transmission.

Figure 3 (e) and (f) shows the same model but with a more zoophilic vector, like *An. arabiensis*, taking 50% of its meals on non-human hosts. The form is very similar, but we see that the slope is shallower. Adding coverage does reduce transmission, and we see that even with 85% coverage, the exposure of the other 15% of non-users is reduced from the baseline-level of 100 bpy to 20 bpy: a worthwhile reduction but still a high level of exposure!

Figure 4: Modelling the short-term effect of increasing ITN coverage on EIR (as infectious bites per person per year), assuming fixed human infectiousness. The first four panels (a) (b) (c) (d) assume an anthropophilic vector like *An. gambiae* in western Kenya, the last two (e) and (f) assume a more zoophilic species like *An. arabiensis* taking half its meals on nonhumans. The left hand panels (a), (c) and (e) show the EIR on unprotected people and on ITN users separately, the right hand panels (b) (d) and (f) show the two groups, users and non-users, combined. The upper panels (a) and (b) show EIR on an arithmetic scale; the four lower panels (c) (d) (e) and (f) use a log scale.

SECTION 4. Insecticide Resistance and its Effect on Personal Protection and the Community Effect.

The last two decades have seen remarkable progress in suppressing the global burden of malaria. This progress could, however, be lost: it is dependent on the maintenance of coverage with effective vector control. The two biggest threats to our ability to “sustain the gains” are weakened political and financial will and insecticide resistance, particularly resistance to pyrethroids, which continue to be used on all currently available ITNs. Sustaining international investment in interventions requires constant effort in the face of competing health problems. This at least can be tracked: we do have good real-time data on the amount being spent and the numbers of nets being deployed (The Alliance for Malaria Prevention, 2020, WHO, 2019). Unfortunately, it is much harder to know whether each net is still having the community-level impact on malaria that we saw before the spread of resistance: for example, in the big trials of the 1990s, and later in the first national-scale distribution campaigns of the mid-2000s.

Since the late 2000s, there has been clear experimental hut evidence that pyrethroid resistant vectors are more likely to succeed in feeding on a host under a pyrethroid-based ITNs, and less likely to be killed as they do so. If so, then there is a clear prediction from our underlying and well-supported ento-epidemiological model: we should expect to see that pyrethroid-based ITNs are less effective at reducing malaria in the

community at large. So, of course the next step should be to go out and measure whether this is really happening, in ITN-using populations-at-risk. Unfortunately, this is not easy to do in practice.

Measuring the impact of resistance on intervention effectiveness is difficult because resistance cannot be assigned randomly to some communities but not others. The evolution of resistance, which is best measured in terms of gene frequencies and geographical spread, can happen quickly or slowly. However, once resistance has reached high frequency in one location, comparable places with little or no resistance are invariably far away.

In a major study coordinated by WHO, a novel study design was employed in an attempt to measure the impact of resistance on intervention effectiveness (Kleinschmidt et al., 2018). The trial compared ITN-users and non-users within villages and was designed around local variation in the level of resistance observed (with WHO tube bioassays) in samples of the village vector populations. On this basis, villages were ranked and divided into two groups, the “high resistance villages” with above-median levels of bioassay survival, and the “low resistance villages” with below-median levels of bioassay survival. The residents of all villages were then given conventional pyrethroid long-lasting insecticidal nets (LLINs), and malaria indices were monitored. The key comparison was incidence of clinical malaria and infection prevalence between ITN-users and non-users in the same villages, which was taken as a measure of intervention effectiveness in that village. The rationale was that if resistance were reducing the protection given by ITNs in high-resistance villages, then the gap between users and non-users (in terms of their malaria indices) would be smaller in the high- than the low-resistance villages. It was observed that net-users did indeed enjoy substantial protection compared to non-users, but there was no association between the magnitude of this protection and the village resistance.

This study was significant because it tried to address a difficult and important question using a novel method. However, the design made some key assumptions. These would have been vindicated, if the study had indeed found the anticipated negative association between resistance and protection. In the absence of this, we must re-examine the two main limitations of the design. In particular, we must consider the possibility that there are village-level factors that could cause both an increase in the observed level of protection given to users compared to non-users, and an increased selection for resistance. Consider for example the likely effects of variation between villages in ITN coverage, both before and during the study. We might expect there to be more intense selection for resistance in villages with higher ITN coverage; this might explain why substantial variation in levels of resistance was observed amongst nearby villages. Coverage might also be associated with bigger differences between ITN-users and non-users – especially if

there is a confounding association with equity. For example, if ITN coverage is only moderately high – say 40% to 70% -- then on the basis of previous studies, we would expect to see only a small difference in the average wealth of users and non-users. But if coverage is very high (e.g. >90%) then it seems very possible that it is the poorest and most socially-excluded residents who end-up as non-users. And since the poorest socio-economic groups are almost always at the highest risk of malaria, this could strengthen the observed contrast between ITN-users and non-users in high-coverage villages. If high coverage villages are also high-resistance villages, this would tend to create a positive association, amongst villages, between resistance and apparent strength of protection. In other words, this kind of process could cancel out the negative association that this study hypothesised and tried to measure.

The second major limitation of this study is that, by comparing users and non-users in the same villages, it only asked about the impact of resistance on personal protection, and could say nothing about its impact on the community effect and village-scale differences in transmission.

In the absence of a satisfactory method of measuring directly the impact of resistance on intervention effectiveness, we must resort to more indirect methods to address this question. Fortunately, two such indirect methods are available; both are quite persuasive.

The first is to go back to underlying theory and use experimental hut measures of ITN effectiveness in preventing feeding (which produces personal protection) and in killing vectors as they try to feed (which produces the community effect). The question then is whether and how much these effects are diminished by resistance. A substantial number of such studies have been carried out, and a separate systematic review of these would be helpful.

Here we mention only a few studies, selected to illustrate the range of approaches that are possible. The first studies of this kind compared the results from experimental huts in two locations, one with a lot of resistance and one with little or no resistance. For example, one particularly convincing and influential study was carried out in Benin (N'Guessan et al., 2007). It showed that in an area with substantial resistance, conventional pyrethroid nets had lost almost all their ability to prevent feeding (compared to an untreated net) and most of their ability to kill blood-seeking females. This data, indirect though it was, had a major influence in building the technical consensus and political will necessary for development of the GPIRM, the WHO's Global Plan for Insecticide Resistance Management (WHO, 2012).

A systematic review summarised the data from experimental hut trials of this kind up to 2013 (which now requires an updated review). It concluded that overall, there is evidence that nets tend to be less effective in areas of high resistance (Strode et al., 2014).

More recently, the deployment of non-pyrethroid sprays, and advent of new LLINs with synergists such as PBO and novel non-pyrethroid active ingredients, has provided evidence of a new especially persuasive kind. Several countries have observed a conspicuous contrast between the impact of conventional pyrethroid nets (for example following a fresh campaign to restore universal coverage) and the impact in a comparable area of nets with PBO, or IRS with a non-pyrethroid. According to some national programme staff, this comparison already provides simple and unarguable evidence that in some locations, conventional pyrethroid nets are no longer performing adequately.

Experimental hut studies with these new nets offer the same kind of comparison but in entomological terms, and show the range of impacts that can be seen, in terms of the measured effects on feeding success and survival of resistant vectors (Bayili et al., 2019, Menze et al., 2020).

Comparing net performance in areas with low and high resistance is useful, but in most places, the genetics of resistance is complex: more than one biochemical mechanism is usually involved, controlled by several genetic loci. In these cases, genetic analysis is needed. A few such studies (e.g. (Kolaczinski et al., 2000)) were carried out doing this with the knockdown resistance gene *kdr*, but it was soon realised that it played only a minor role in resistance, most of which was due to other metabolic resistance mechanisms for which assays exist but are often difficult to implement.

For several years there were no such markers for the main resistance mechanisms in *An. gambiae* and *An. funestus*. Now, we have DNA-markers for just a few examples, but most resistance cannot yet be routinely scored at the DNA level. It is hard to overstate the importance of this obstacle, as a factor preventing not only basic observations (such as monitoring the evolution and spread of resistance in mosquito populations) but also studies of the impact of resistance on mosquito outcomes at the individual level, in bioassays and experimental huts.

DISCUSSION

The barrier provided by sleeping under an ITN prevents vectors from feeding on the user, and thus offers personal protection. This effect is immediate and local. In addition, and because some vectors are killed,

thus affecting the local mosquito population, there can also be a community effect, giving additional protection to everyone in the local area, including people not sleeping under a net.

The very first experimental hut trials observed that a proportion of blood-seeking females were killed as they tried to feed on someone using an ITN. From this observation, it was predicted that as well as giving personal protection, ITNs might also be able to reduce the average longevity, and thus the vectorial capacity, of local mosquito populations. This prediction was based on Macdonald's theories from the 1950s, emphasising the importance of vector longevity as a determinant of transmission intensity, and proposing that the dramatic impact of IRS on transmission was mediated primarily by effects on longevity. In the case of IRS, Macdonald's theory was strongly supported, in entomological and epidemiological terms, by the studies and trials of IRS in the 1960s and 1970s. In the case of ITNs, that prediction made in 1984, was then thoroughly confirmed by the studies and trials of the 1990s.

Entomological data confirming a reduction in density and/or sporozoite rates has been seen many trials, and in one trial using particularly detailed methods of age-grading, an effect on longevity was clearly shown to be the main mechanism mediating this local reduction in transmission, this "community effect".

Further epidemiological evidence, showing protection for non-net-users living within or near to a community with a high level of ITN coverage, soon followed. As with the entomological evidence, some of the key details about this epidemiological protection – for example the distance over which measurable protection extended beyond the limits of treated villages – were again remarkably consistent with what we would expect from the underlying theory combined with prior biological knowledge about mosquito movement.

So we have explained the emergence, in the 1990s, of a theoretical understanding of the ento-epidemiological mode of action of ITNs. Then, in a systematic review of epidemiological trials that collected suitable evidence to assess the community effect, we found that the results of the selected trials were remarkably consistent with that theory of ento-epidemiological mechanisms. Of course, the trials included in our review represent only a small fraction of the large and diverse body of evidence on ITN effectiveness that has accumulated from the many ITN effectiveness studies that have been conducted over the last 25 years. So it is worth noting that, despite this large volume of research, that model of the ento-epidemiological mode of action of ITNs was not substantially challenged or altered by any of the new evidence that has emerged over this period.

Nevertheless, there are still many important knowledge gaps concerning the community effect. This appears to be because, since the early studies in the 80s and 90s, ITN trials have been mainly designed to measure the combined effect of personal protection plus the community effect, rather than to measure their relative contributions to the overall benefit. Consider, for example, the various contextual factors that are expected to moderate the strength of the community:

- Species-specific host-preference (which varies between *Anopheles* species)
- Relative availability of non-human and human hosts in the locality.
- ITN Coverage (including usage)
- The nature of the insecticide: its residual insecticidal activity (and hence age of ITNs) and repellency
- Vector resistance to insecticide(s) on net – genetically determined, varying between species and between locations.

After 25 years of experimentation and epidemiological modelling, there remain many gaps in our knowledge of whether these factors do indeed have the expected moderating influence on the strength of the community effect. The point is perhaps best made by some illustrative exceptions. For example, in some locations, the scaling up of ITNs has affected the balance of sibling species within the *gambiae* complex. In parts of Uganda and Kenya near to Lake Victoria, for example, *An. gambiae s.s.* used to be much more numerous than *An. arabiensis*. Sustained high levels of ITN coverage have suppressed both species to lower densities than before, but *gambiae* has been affected more than *arabiensis*, so that *arabiensis* is now the more abundant of the two. This is indirect but clear evidence that as expected, the more anthropophilic species (*gambiae s.s.*) was more affected by the killing effect of insecticide than the more zoophilic one (*arabiensis*).

One of the most important knowledge gaps concerns the scale over which a community effect is expected to occur. As explained above, we remain frustratingly uncertain about the absence of an observable community effect between treated and untreated villages in the Gambian National Impregnated Bednet Program. Was this because the vectors were being repelled but not killed? Or was it because there was too much mixing between mosquito populations of treated and untreated villages, perhaps reflecting the long distance, in this arid setting, between villages and major breeding sites? The design of a cluster-randomised vector control trial assumes that villages are perfect “transmission units”, such that within a village, mosquitoes move freely and randomly between people, but there is no exchange of people or mosquitoes between villages. In reality, of course, this separation is never perfect, but it can be enough, at least in some settings: very clear community effects have been seen in contrasts between small villages separated by short distances (e.g. (Magesa et al., 1991)). However, at the moment, it seems to be assumed that because we

have seen such contrasts in some cases, we can assume that this will also be the case elsewhere – when in fact there is plenty of evidence that mosquito dispersal distances vary widely between settings. In general, we should probably pay more attention to the risks of small cluster size and the possibility of contamination/spill-over between clusters (Lines and Kleinschmidt, 2015). One way to measure the risk is to routinely geo-reference all households in the cohort, and then analyse whether households near to the edge of treated villages are less well protected than those in the centre.

Another critical knowledge gap is the effect of insecticide resistance on both personal protection and the community effect. Unfortunately, it is close-to-impossible to measure, with precision and without bias, the impact of resistance on epidemiological outcomes. However, we can observe how resistance has altered ITN effects on entomological indicators (feeding success and mortality) in experimental huts: indeed, frightening results from studies of this kind were very influential in driving the development of the WHO's Global Plan for Insecticide Resistance Management in Malaria Vectors (GPIRM) (WHO, 2012, Mnzava et al., 2015). A systematic review of the effect of resistance on experimental hut outcomes would be timely and useful.

In addition, experimenters should be striving to identify the effect of specific polymorphic resistance genes on an individual female mosquito's probability of feeding success and survival, as in the study by Kolaczinski et al. (Kolaczinski et al., 2000). Doing this with the most important cytochrome-mediated resistance mechanisms has been difficult, because in most cases we lack the DNA-level markers needed to score for genotype in insects that have been dead for several hours. The ability to score DNA-level markers in experimental hut samples would represent a radical advance in our ability to compare the performance of alternative new-generation LLIN products, and to adapt the deployment of these products according to the resistance mechanisms in target areas. This in turn would transform our ability to avoid losing the resistance arms-race with mosquitoes.

Mosquito behaviour varies widely between mosquito species. We have known since the 1950s that different vector species – even closely related species such as *An. gambiae* and *An. arabiensis* – can respond very differently to any given intervention. Repeated IRS trials in the 1960s showed that with the indoor-resting *An. gambiae* and *An. funestus*, a good IRS program could more or less interrupt transmission. Achieving this degree of control was much harder against *An. arabiensis*, because of its greater tendency to sometimes rest outdoors. Eventually, there grew up a consensus understanding that this property of *An. arabiensis* meant that IRS would not be able to interrupt transmission in much of Africa,

and that for this reason it was no longer realistic to hope for global eradication of malaria with current technologies.

Just as indoor- and outdoor-resting is important for IRS, so anthropophily and zoophily are similarly important for ITNs. We have seen that the community effect is mediated by the killing of blood-seeking females as they try to feed on someone under an ITN: there is an effect on longevity because the risk of being killed is cumulative and repeated in every cycle. Or more precisely, it is repeated every time a human bloodmeal is sought: there is no such risk when trying to feed on a horse, because horses do not use ITNs! Thus the strength of the community effect is expected to vary with the proportion of bloodmeals taken on ITN-using hosts. And so it is expected to be less strong when many bloodmeals are taken on non-human hosts, or when coverage of the human population is low.

It is important to note that the evidence base discussed in this paper is almost exclusively from sub-Saharan Africa. Although some trials in the Cochrane review are from Asia and Latin America, they did not measure or report epidemiological or entomological outcomes in such a way as to separate personal protection from community-level effects.

Evidence from a number of the studies included in our data synthesis of randomised trials identified a dose response between increasing ITN use and increased level of community effect [refs]. This is confirmed by mathematical models which demonstrate that the relationship between ITN use and impact on malaria transmission is non-linear. Specifying a defined threshold for when the community effect starts or ends is challenging given the strong influence of context on the relationship. However, the models show that the community effect is evident even at low levels of ITN coverage, and continues to at least 85% coverage. Therefore, increasing ITN coverage (use) will always achieve an increase in community effect supporting the aim for universal coverage in the existing WHO guidelines. However, these findings inevitably must be placed in the context of limited finite resources under which national programmes make their decisions. The incremental costs of achieving further gains in ITN use where high use has already been achieved are likely to be greater than costs of delivery when initially scaling up ITN coverage, the so-called pattern of “diminishing coverage returns for each dollar spent” suggested by Bhatt et al {Bhatt, 2015 #53}. This is an important cost-effectiveness analysis that needs to be done to inform ITN deployment decisions and the most efficient use of resources for malaria control as a whole.

CONCLUSION

There is no doubt that the community effect can and does happen. There is now a remarkable consensus, between malaria entomologists and malaria epidemiological modellers, about the two basic elements of how ITNs work, and the aspects of mosquito biology and behaviour that underlie these effects. Various contextual factors can influence the magnitude of the community effect. These include vector behaviour (particularly degree of anthropophily), level of ITN use, insecticide lethality, and insecticide resistance. However, even considering all of these contextual factors. With an anthropophilic vector, the community effect brings significant area-wide benefits range across the range of practicable coverage from 15% to 85%: there is no required minimum level of coverage, and additional coverage is always beneficial.

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Table 1: Overview of epidemiological evidence available from clinical trials to compare personal versus community-level protection of insecticide-treated nets (ITNs)

Study	Malaria epidemiology	Overview of intervention	Epidemiological results			
			Personal protection only ¹	Combined personal and community level protection ²	Personal protection versus community level protection ³	Risk of bias assessment ⁴
(country; years of intervention; refs)	Transmission intensity; main parasite.	Study design; intervention vs control (no. clusters or individuals per arm); target population; net material; insecticide (target dose); net use	Mortality; clinical malaria (by species); severe malaria; parasitaemia (by species); anaemia	Mortality; clinical malaria (by species); severe malaria; parasitaemia (by species); anaemia	Mortality; clinical malaria (by species); severe malaria; parasitaemia (by species); anaemia	
Ghana, 1993-95 (Binka et al., 1998, Binka et al., 1996)	Endemic, seasonal; <i>P. falciparum</i>	cRCT; ITN (n=48) vs no net (n=48); all population; nylon; permethrin (500mg/m ²); ITN use in int areas Y1 rainy season: 97%, Y1 dry season: 65%, Y2 rainy: 72%, Y2 dry: 50%, in cont areas: NR		<u>All-cause mortality</u> (6-59mo) (deaths per 1000 child-years): Int: 23.5 (396/16841); Cont: 27.9 (461/16495); RR (95% CI): 0.83 (0.69, 1.00; p=0.05)	<u>All-cause mortality rate</u> amongst non-users (in control HHs) increased with distance from nearest HH with ITNs (p=0.007). Each increase of 100m away from the boundary associated with an increased mortality risk of individuals without ITNs of 6.7% (1.8-11.4%).	Low risk
The Gambia, 1992-93 (D'Alessandro et al., 1995a, D'Alessandro et al., 1995b, Thomson et al., 1995a, Thomson et al., 1995b)	Moderate, seasonal; <i>P. falciparum</i>	cRCT; ITN (treating existing nets; n=52) vs UTN/no net (n=52); existing net owners; NR; permethrin (200mg/m ²); Pre-int use of any net: 46%-79%, post-int use of ITN in int areas: 56%-94% (varied		<u>All-cause mortality (1-9y)</u> (deaths per 1000 child-years): Int: 8.1 (162/19907); Cont: 10.4 (235/22692); adj RR (95% CI): 0.75 (0.57, 0.98; p=0.04) <u><i>P. falciparum</i> PR:</u> Int: 36.1% (288/797); Cont:	<u><i>P. falciparum</i> PR:</u> ITN users, Int clusters: 27%, UTN users, Int: 22%; Cont: 30%; No net, Int: 60%; Cont: 45%	Low risk

Table 1: Overview of epidemiological evidence available from clinical trials to compare personal versus community-level protection of insecticide-treated nets (ITNs)

Study	Malaria epidemiology	Overview of intervention	Epidemiological results			
			Personal protection only ¹	Combined personal and community level protection ²	Personal protection versus community level protection ³	Risk of bias assessment ⁴
		by area), in cont areas: NR		38.7% (280/723); RR (95% CI): 0.75 (P>0.05)		
Tanzania, 1996 (Fraser-Hurt et al., 1999)	Intense, perennial; <i>P. falciparum</i>	RCT; ITN (n=60 children) vs no net (n=60); individual allocation (0-59 mo); NR; permethrin (500mg/m ²); ITN use in int areas: 97%, UTN use in cont areas: 23%	<u>Mean <i>P. falciparum</i> PR</u> (children 5-24 mo): Int: 46%; Cont: 65%; LRT Chi-sq=6.2; p=0.013. <u>Mean Hb</u> : Int: 93.4g/L; Cont: 88.2g/L; Wilcoxon's Z=2.51; p=0.012			High risk ⁵
Cote d'Ivoire, 1999-2000 (Henry et al., 2005)	Intense, perennial; <i>P. falciparum</i> , <i>P. malariae</i>	cRCT; ITN (n=4) vs no net (n=4); all population; NR; lambda-cyhalothrin (15mg/m ²); ITN use in int areas: 77%-84% (varied by village), in cont areas: NR		<u>Incidence of clinical malaria</u> (per child-year): Int: 0.8 (0.4, 1.2); Cont: 1.8 (1.3, 2.4); RR: 0.43 (0.25-0.74; p<0.01) <u>Mean <i>P. falciparum</i> PR</u> (children 0-59 mo): Int: 56.6% (549/970); Cont: 68.5% (624/911); p<0.001 <u>PCV</u> (0-23mo): Int: 32.8% (27/83); Cont: 30.8% (22/72); p=0.007		High risk ⁶
Thailand, 1987-88 (Kamol-	Endemic, perennial; <i>P. falciparum</i> , <i>P. vivax</i>	RCT; ITN (n=131) vs UTN (n=139); individual allocation (migrant workers); nylon;	<u>Incidence of clinical malaria</u> , any species (per 1000 person-weeks): Int: 6.35 (28/4410); Cont:			Low risk

Table 1: Overview of epidemiological evidence available from clinical trials to compare personal versus community-level protection of insecticide-treated nets (ITNs)

Study	Malaria epidemiology	Overview of intervention	Epidemiological results			
			Personal protection only ¹	Combined personal and community level protection ²	Personal protection versus community level protection ³	Risk of bias assessment ⁴
Ratanakul and Prasittisuk, 1992)		permethrin (500mg/m ²); net use 70%-80% (across int & cont areas)	10.79 (51/4725); chi-sq 4.75; P=0.029			
Colombia, 1993-94 (Kroeger et al., 1995)	Hypoendemic, unstable, seasonal; <i>P. falciparum</i> (69%), <i>P. vivax</i>	cRCT; ITN (n=11) vs UTN (n=11); all population; polyester; lambda-hycalothrin (10-30mg/m ²); pre-int UTN use all year (int & cont): 67%-80%, treatment uptake in int areas: 59%		<u>Incidence of clinical malaria</u> , any species (per 4-months): Int: 2.3; Cont: 7.9; RR: 0.29 (0.2-0.4; p<0.001)		High risk ⁷
Ecuador, 1991-94 (Kroeger et al., 1995)	Hypoendemic, unstable, seasonal; <i>P. falciparum</i> (50-88%), <i>P. vivax</i>	cRCT; ITN (n=7) vs UTN (n=7); all population; cotton; permethrin (200mg/m ²); pre-int UTN use all year (int & cont): 67%-80%, treatment uptake in int areas: 68%-80%		<u>Incidence of clinical malaria</u> , any species (per 4-months): Int: 3.7; Cont: 4.6; RR: 0.80 (0.5-1.2; p>0.05)		High risk ⁷
Peru - coastal, 1991-93 (Kroeger et al., 1995)	Hypoendemic, unstable, seasonal; <i>P. vivax</i>	cRCT; ITN (n=6) vs UTN (n=6); all population; polyester; Y1: lambda-hycalothrin (10mg/m ²) Y2: permethrin (500mg/m ²); pre-int UTN use rainy season		<u>Incidence of clinical malaria</u> , any species (per 4-months): Int: 27.4; Cont: 30.3; RR: 0.90 (0.8-1.0; p=0.008)		High risk ⁷

Table 1: Overview of epidemiological evidence available from clinical trials to compare personal versus community-level protection of insecticide-treated nets (ITNs)

Study	Malaria epidemiology	Overview of intervention	Epidemiological results			
			Personal protection only ¹	Combined personal and community level protection ²	Personal protection versus community level protection ³	Risk of bias assessment ⁴
		(int & cont): 54%, treatment uptake in int areas: 66%				
Peru - Amazon, 1991-92 (Kroeger et al., 1995)	Hypoendemic, perennial; <i>P. vivax</i>	cRCT; ITN (n=18) vs UTN (n=18); all population; polyester; cotton; permethrin (200mg/m ²); pre-int UTN use (int & cont): 67%-80%, treatment uptake in int areas: 61%		<u>Incidence of clinical malaria</u> , any species (per 4-months): Int: 3.7; Cont: 5.5; RR: 0.67 (0.5-0.8; p=0.002)		High risk ⁸
Nicaragua, 1994-96 (Kroeger et al., 1999)	Seasonal; <i>P. vivax</i>	cRCT; ITN (n=13) vs UTN (n=13); all population; nylon; lambda-hycalothrin (12.5mg/m ²); ITN use in int areas in Y1: 51%, outcomes in Y2 stratified by ITN use, UTN use in cont areas: 25%		<u>Incidence of clinical vivax malaria</u> (per 4-months) <u>ITN coverage 31-70%</u> : Int: 2.5 (63/2530); Cont: 7.8 (212/2730); 0.32 (0.24-0.42; p<0.001) <u>ITN coverage 16-30%</u> : Int: 5.0 (62/1242); Cont: 7.3 (113/1557); 0.68 (0.51-0.93; 0.01) <u>ITN coverage <16%</u> : Int: 6.3 (80/1269); Cont: 6.3 (97/1528); 1.0 (p>0.05)		High risk ⁹

Table 1: Overview of epidemiological evidence available from clinical trials to compare personal versus community-level protection of insecticide-treated nets (ITNs)

Study	Malaria epidemiology	Overview of intervention	Epidemiological results			
			Personal protection only ¹	Combined personal and community level protection ²	Personal protection versus community level protection ³	Risk of bias assessment ⁴
Thai-Burmese border, 1990-91 (Luxemburger et al., 1994)	Unstable, seasonal; <i>P. falciparum</i> , <i>P. vivax</i>	RCT; ITN (n=175) vs UTN (n=175); individual allocation (4-15 year-olds); cotton; permethrin (500mg/m ²); 93% use (ITN in int areas, UTN in cont areas)	<p><u>Incidence of clinical falciparum malaria</u> (per 1000 child-months): Int: 37.5 (33/933); Cont: 60.7 (57/939); RR: 0.58 (0.38-0.89).</p> <p><u>Incidence of clinical vivax malaria</u> (per 1000 child-months): Int: 37.5 (35/933); Cont: 47.9 (45/939); RR: 0.78 (0.51-1.21)</p> <p><u><i>P. falciparum</i> PR</u>: Int: 6.8% (10/147); Cont: 8.5% (13/153); p>0.05</p> <p><u><i>P. vivax</i> PR</u>: Int: 2.0% (3/147); Cont: 3.9% (6/153); p>0.05</p>			Low risk
Venezuela, 1999-2000 (Magris et al., 2007)	Perennial; <i>P. falciparum</i> , <i>P. vivax</i> , <i>P. malariae</i>	cRCT; insecticide-treated hammock nets (ITHN; n=9) vs placebo-treated hammock nets (PTHN; n=9); all population; nylon; lambda-cyhalothrin (10mg/m ²); net use: NR		<p><u>Incidence of clinical falciparum malaria</u> (per 1000 person-years): Int: 63.8 (73/835); Cont: 106.6 (108/917); RR: 0.46 (0.40-0.53; p=0.03)</p> <p><u>Incidence of clinical vivax malaria</u> (per 1000 person-</p>		Some concerns ¹⁰

Table 1: Overview of epidemiological evidence available from clinical trials to compare personal versus community-level protection of insecticide-treated nets (ITNs)

Study	Malaria epidemiology	Overview of intervention	Epidemiological results			
			Personal protection only ¹	Combined personal and community level protection ²	Personal protection versus community level protection ³	Risk of bias assessment ⁴
				<p>years): Int: 64.5 (52/649); Cont: 87.6 (71/790); RR: 0.74 (0-1.40; p=0.24)</p> <p><u>All species PR</u>: Int: 2.8%; Cont: 10.4%; 0.17 (0-0.53; p=0.01)</p> <p><u>Mean Hb</u>: Int: 11.6g/dL; Cont: 12g/dL; p=0.61</p>		
Sierra Leone, 1992-93 (Magbity et al., 1997, Marbiah et al., 1998)	Hyperendemic, perennial; <i>P. falciparum</i>	cRCT; ITN (n=8) vs no nets (n=8); nylon; all population; lambda-cyhalothrin (10mg/m ²); net use: NR		<p><u>Incidence of clinical falciparum malaria</u> (per 1000 child-weeks): Int: 19.2 (309/16126); Cont: 37.7 (576/15269); RR: 0.51 (0.44, 0.58)</p> <p>Mean haematocrit: Int: 43.4%; Cont: 38% (p=?)</p>		Low risk
Cameroon, 1992 (Moyou-Somo et al., 1995)	Intense, perennial; <i>P. falciparum</i>	cRCT; ITN (n=2) vs no nets (n=2); all population; NR; deltamethrin (25mg/m ²); net use: NR		<u><i>P. falciparum</i> PR</u> : Int: 29% (321/1107); Cont: 41% (443/1083); RR: 1.37 (1.12-1.68; p=0.002)		Some concerns ¹¹
Kenya - coastal, 1993-95 (Howard et al., 2000, Mbogo et al.,	Seasonal; <i>P. falciparum</i>	cRCT; ITN (n=28) vs no nets (n=28); all population; polyester; permethrin (500mg/m ²); ITN use by		<p><u>All-cause mortality</u> (12-59mo) (per 1000 child-years): Int: 7.4 (70/9466); Cont: 10.9 (104/9556);</p>	<p><u>Severe malaria admissions</u> (1-59mo), cohort analysis: Int clusters: ITN users: 5.8% (95/1626), non-ITN users:</p>	Low risk

Table 1: Overview of epidemiological evidence available from clinical trials to compare personal versus community-level protection of insecticide-treated nets (ITNs)

Study	Malaria epidemiology	Overview of intervention	Epidemiological results			
			Personal protection only ¹	Combined personal and community level protection ²	Personal protection versus community level protection ³	Risk of bias assessment ⁴
1996, Nevill et al., 1996)		under-fives in int areas: 77% rainy season, 65% dry season, in cont areas: <1%		Adj RR: 0.67 (0.49, 0.93; p=0.02) <u>Severe malaria admissions</u> (1-59mo): Int:: 11.0 (127/1155); Cont: 20.0 (229/1145); Adj RR: 0.56 (0.38, 0.81; p=0.004)	7.3% (13/179), p>0.05; Cont clusters: 12.6% (257/2048); non-ITN users in int clusters: 7.3% (13/179) (p=0.05)	
Kenya – western, 1997-99 (Gimnig et al., 2003a, Gimnig et al., 2003b, Hawley et al., 2003, Phillips-Howard et al., 2003, ter Kuile et al., 2003)	Intense, holoendemic, perennial; <i>P. falciparum</i> , <i>P. malariae</i>	cRCT; ITN (n=113) vs no nets (n=108); all population; polyester; permethrin (500mg/m ²); ITN use in int areas: 70%, ITN ownership in cont areas: 2.6%		<u>All-cause mortality</u> (1-11mo) (per 1000 child-years): Int: 102.3 (376/3677); Cont: 133.3 (492/3691); RR: 0.77 (0.67-0.88; p=0.0001) <u>All-cause mortality</u> (1-59mo) (per 1000 child-years): Int: 43.9 (782/17833); Cont: 51.9 (940/18099); RR: 0.84 (0.77-0.93; p=0.0005) <u>HD falciparum PR (<36mo)</u> : Int: 18.0% (173/960); Cont: 25.9% (234/902); p=? <u>Mean Hb</u> : Int: 10.0 g/dL; Cont: 9.5 g/dL (p<0.001)	<u>Child mortality, moderate anaemia, high-density parasitaemia, HB levels</u> : protective effect in control HHs located within 300m of an ITN HH. Strength of community effect depended on high coverage with ITNs in neighbouring HHs (>50%).	Low risk (mortality outcome) High risk (morbidity outcomes) ¹²

Table 1: Overview of epidemiological evidence available from clinical trials to compare personal versus community-level protection of insecticide-treated nets (ITNs)

Study	Malaria epidemiology	Overview of intervention	Epidemiological results			
			Personal protection only ¹	Combined personal and community level protection ²	Personal protection versus community level protection ³	Risk of bias assessment ⁴
Pakistan, 1991-92 (Rowland et al., 1996)	NR; <i>P. vivax</i> , <i>P. falciparum</i>	RCT; ITN (n=1398) vs no nets (n=1394); HH allocation (10% refugee camp HHs); polyester; permethrin (500mg/m ²); ITN use in int areas: 73%, ITN use in cont areas: 2%	<p><u>Incidence of clinical falciparum malaria</u> (per 100 persons): Int: 3.8 (53/1395); Cont: 9.9 (138/1394); RR: 0.39 (0.29, 0.53; p<0.001)</p> <p><u>Incidence of clinical vivax malaria</u> (per 1000 person-years): Int: 13.0 (182/1395); Cont: 22.4 (313/1397); RR: 0.58 (0.49, 0.68; p<0.001)</p> <p><u>Falciparum PR</u>: Int: 3.7% (35/956); Cont: 6.4% (71/1116); RR: 0.57 (0.37, 0.86; p=0.009)</p> <p><u>Mean Hb</u>: Int: 11.6g/dL; Cont: 12g/dL; p=0.61</p>			Some concerns ¹³
Kenya, 1988 (Sexton et al., 1990)	Holoendemic, perennial; <i>P. falciparum</i>	RCT; ITN (n=166) vs no nets (n=159); HH allocation; nylon/polyester; permethrin (500mg/m ²); ITN use in int areas: 73%, ITN use in cont areas: 2%	<p><u>Incidence of clinical falciparum malaria</u> (per 100 person-weeks): Int: 3.8 (55/1458); Cont: 5.4 (75/1384); RR: 0.70 (0.48, 1.00)</p>			Some concerns ¹⁴

Table 1: Overview of epidemiological evidence available from clinical trials to compare personal versus community-level protection of insecticide-treated nets (ITNs)

Study	Malaria epidemiology	Overview of intervention	Epidemiological results			
			Personal protection only ¹	Combined personal and community level protection ²	Personal protection versus community level protection ³	Risk of bias assessment ⁴
Myanmar, 1998-99 (Smithuis et al., 2013a, Smithuis et al., 2013b)	Mesoendemic, perennial; <i>P. falciparum</i> , <i>P. vivax</i>	cRCT; ITN (n=10) vs no nets (n=10); all population; polyester; deltamethrin (25mg/m ²); ITN use in int areas: 84%, UTN use in cont areas: 7%		<p><u>Incidence of clinical falciparum malaria</u> (per 1000 weeks exposure): Int: 2.5 (351/141,903); Cont: 4.9 (713/144694); weighted paired test: p=0.22</p> <p><u><i>P. falciparum</i> PR</u>: Int: 4.2% (161/3859); Cont: 5.7% (225/3969); p=0.30</p> <p><u><i>P. vivax</i> PR</u>: Int: 11.6% (446/3859); Cont: 14.2% (564/3969); p=0.30</p> <p><u>Hb < 10g/dL</u>: Int: 60.6% (2338/3857); Cont: 64.2% (2547/3965); p=0.38</p>		Low risk
The Gambia, 1987 (Lindsay et al., 1989, Snow et al., 1988)	Moderate, seasonal; <i>P. falciparum</i>	cRCT; ITN (n=7) vs UTN (n=9); all population; synthetic; permethrin (500mg/m ²); ITN use in int areas: 82%; UTN use in cont areas: 94%		<p><u>Incidence of clinical falciparum malaria</u> (per 1000 person-weeks): Int: 4.1 (16/3027); Cont: 14.4 (49/3299); RR: 0.28 (0.13, 0.59; p<0.001)</p> <p><u><i>P. falciparum</i> PR</u>: Int: 30.9% (58/189); Cont: 37.3% (87/233); RR: 0.68 (0.40, 1.14; p=0.21)</p>		Low risk

Table 1: Overview of epidemiological evidence available from clinical trials to compare personal versus community-level protection of insecticide-treated nets (ITNs)

Study	Malaria epidemiology	Overview of intervention	Epidemiological results			
			Personal protection only ¹	Combined personal and community level protection ²	Personal protection versus community level protection ³	Risk of bias assessment ⁴
				PCV: Int: 35.8; Cont: 33.1; p=0.032		
Cambodia, 2001-02 (Sochantha et al., 2006)	Perennial; <i>P. falciparum</i> , <i>P. vivax</i>	cRCT; ITN (n=17) vs no net (n=17); all population; polyester; deltamethrin (25mg/m ²); post-int ITN use in int areas: 87%; post-int ITN use in cont areas: 14%		<u><i>P. falciparum</i>-positive consultations</u> per person per year (adj): Int: 0.20 (39/359); Cont: 0.36 (89/272); Adj: 0.72 (0.47, 1.08; p=0.106) <u><i>P. falciparum</i> PR</u> : Int: 16%; Cont: 18%; RR: 0.90 (0.63, 1.30; p=0.56)		Low risk

CI = confidence interval; cont = control group; cRCT = cluster randomised controlled trial; Hb = haemoglobin; HD = high density [parasitaemia]; HH = household; int = intervention group; ITHN = insecticide-treated hammock net; ITN = insecticide-treated net; LRT = likelihood ratio test; mo = months-old; NR = not reported; PCV = packed cell volume; PR = parasite prevalence; PTHN = placebo-treated hammock net; RCT = randomised controlled trial; RR = risk ratio; UTN = untreated net.

¹Epidemiological outcomes reported by individually-randomised studies; ²Epidemiological outcomes from per protocol analysis of cRCT; ³Epidemiological outcomes from cRCT, reported separately for users and non-users in intervention and control clusters, or spatial analysis of epidemiological outcomes amongst ITN non-users by proximity to intervention clusters. ⁴Full details of risk assessment provided for each study in table 2. ⁵Randomisation reported but process not described; Pre-int prevalence different between int (54.1%) and control (65%) groups. ⁶Randomisation reported but process not described; nurses assessing sickness during ACD not blinded to study arm; loss to follow up reported but not by arm so biases may be masked. ⁷Randomisation reported but process not described; Malaria incidence included self-reported malaria attacks over 4-month recall period; Insufficient detail on attrition; Baseline 4-month incidence rate significantly different between intervention and control arms. ⁸Randomisation reported but process not described; Malaria incidence included self-reported malaria attacks over 4-month recall period; Insufficient detail on attrition. ⁹Allocation concealment process not described; Malaria incidence included self-reported malaria attacks over 4-month recall period; Insufficient detail on attrition. ¹⁰Missing data not described by arm and reasons not provided. ¹¹Randomisation reported but process not described; insufficient detail provided to assess loss to follow up; baseline prevalence not reported. ¹²Main mortality trial included children aged 1 to 59 months, but only children aged <36 months were sampled for the morbidity analysis. ¹³Randomisation reported but process not described; No reason for missing data provided. ¹⁴Randomisation reported but process not described; Baseline prevalence not reported

Table 2: Overview of risk of bias analysis for studies included in literature review

Author, pub year	Overall assessment of bias ¹	Selection bias		Performance bias	Detection bias		Attrition bias	Reporting bias	Other bias	Notes on reasons for judgement of high bias or some concerns within individual domains of bias
		Random sequence generation	Allocation concealment	Blinding of participants & personnel	Blinding outcome assessment (self-reported fever)	Blinding outcome assessment (all other outcomes)	Incomplete outcome data	Selective reporting	Baseline imbalance	
Binka 1996	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	NA	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	
D'Alessandro 1995	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	NA	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	
Fraser-Hurt 1999	High risk	Some concerns	Some concerns	Low risk	NA	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	High risk	Randomisation reported but process not described; Pre-int prevalence different between int (54.1%) and control (65%) groups
Henry 2005	High risk	Some concerns	Some concerns	Low risk	Some concerns	Low risk	Some concerns	Low risk	Low risk	Randomisation reported but process not described; nurses assessing sickness during ACD not blinded to study arm; loss to follow up reported but not by arm so biases may be masked
Kamol-Ratanakul, 1992	Low risk ²	Some concerns	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Randomisation reported but process not described
Kroeger, 1995	High risk	Some concerns	Some concerns	Low risk	High risk	NA	Some concerns	Low risk	High risk	Randomisation reported but process not described; Malaria incidence included self-reported malaria attacks over 4-month recall period; Insufficient detail on attrition; Baseline 4-month incidence rate sig lower in intervention group
Kroeger, 1995	High risk	Some concerns	Some concerns	Low risk	High risk	NA	Some concerns	Low risk	Low risk	Randomisation reported but process not described; Malaria incidence included self-reported malaria attacks over 4-month recall period; Insufficient detail on attrition
Kroeger, 1995	High risk	Some concerns	Some concerns	Low risk	High risk	NA	Some concerns	Low risk	High risk	Randomisation reported but process not described; Malaria incidence included self-reported malaria attacks over 4-month

Table 2: Overview of risk of bias analysis for studies included in literature review

Author, pub year	Overall assessment of bias ¹	Selection bias		Performance bias	Detection bias		Attrition bias	Reporting bias	Other bias	Notes on reasons for judgement of high bias or some concerns within individual domains of bias
		Random sequence generation	Allocation concealment	Blinding of participants & personnel	Blinding outcome assessment (self-reported fever)	Blinding outcome assessment (all other outcomes)	Incomplete outcome data	Selective reporting	Baseline imbalance	
										recall period; Insufficient detail on attrition; Baseline 4-month incidence rate sig higher in intervention group
Kroeger, 1995	High risk	Some concerns	Some concerns	Low risk	High risk	NA	Some concerns	Low risk	Low risk	Randomisation reported but process not described; Malaria incidence included self-reported malaria attacks over 4-month recall period; Insufficient detail on attrition;
Kroeger, 1999	High risk	Low risk	Some concerns	Low risk	High risk	NA	Some concerns	Low risk	Low risk	Allocation concealment process not described; Malaria incidence included self-reported malaria attacks over 4-month recall period; Insufficient detail on attrition;
Luxemburger, 1994	Low risk ²	Low risk	Some concerns	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Allocation concealment process not described
Magris, 2007	Some concerns	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Some concerns	Low risk	Low risk	Missing data not described by arm and reasons not provided
Marbiah 1998	Low risk ³	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Some concerns	NA	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Self-reported fever during ACD confirmed by blood smear
Moyou-Somo 1995	Some concerns	Some concerns	Some concerns	Low risk	NA	Low risk	Some concerns	Low risk	Some concerns	Randomisation reported but process not described; Insufficient detail provided to assess loss to follow up; Baseline prevalence not reported
Nevill 1996	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	
Phillips-Howard 2003; ter Kuile 2003	Low risk (mortality outcome)	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk (mortality)	Low risk	Low risk	Main mortality trial included children aged 1 to 59 months, but only children <36

Table 2: Overview of risk of bias analysis for studies included in literature review

Author, pub year	Overall assessment of bias ¹	Selection bias		Performance bias	Detection bias		Attrition bias	Reporting bias	Other bias	Notes on reasons for judgement of high bias or some concerns within individual domains of bias
		Random sequence generation	Allocation concealment	Blinding of participants & personnel	Blinding outcome assessment (self-reported fever)	Blinding outcome assessment (all other outcomes)	Incomplete outcome data	Selective reporting	Baseline imbalance	
	High risk (morbidity outcomes)						High risk (morbidity)			months were sampled for the morbidity analysis.
Rowland, 1996	Some concerns	Some concerns	Some concerns	Low risk	Some concerns	Low risk		Low risk	Low risk	Randomisation reported but process not described; Incidence monitored by PCD but cases confirmed by microscopy; No reason for missing data provided
Sexton, 1990	Some concerns	Some concerns	Some concerns	Low risk	NA	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Some concerns	Randomisation reported but process not described; Baseline prevalence not reported
Smithuis, 2013a	Low risk ³	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Some concerns	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Incidence monitored by PCD but cases confirmed by microscopy
Snow 1988	Low risk ²	Some concerns	Some concerns	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Randomisation reported but process not described
Sochantha, 2006	Low risk ^{2,3}	Low risk	Some concerns	Low risk	Some concerns	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Low risk	Allocation concealment process not reported; Incidence monitored by PCD but cases confirmed by RDT

Abbreviations: ACD = active case detection; NA = not applicable (outcome not measured); PCD = passive case detection; RDT = rapid diagnostic test

¹Overall judgement of bias: Low risk = the trial is judged to be at low risk of bias for all domains, or where there are some concerns in one of the domains, these were not judged to be reason to consider the trial at unclear risk overall (further detail given for specific trials); Some concerns = the trial is judged to raise some concerns in two or more domains, but not to be at high risk of bias for any domain; High risk = The trial is judged to be at high risk of bias in at least one domain for this result, or the trial is judged to have some concerns for multiple domains in a way that substantially lowers confidence in the result. ²Although randomisation process not described, intervention and control groups were similar at baseline. ³Although suspected malaria cases were identified by self-reporting, these were parasitologically-confirmed (by microscopy or rapid diagnostic test) before inclusion in the result.

Table 3: Overview of available entomological evidence from clinical trials to compare personal versus community-level protection of insecticide-treated nets (ITNs)

Study	Malaria entomology	Overview of intervention	Entomological data collection	Entomological results			
				Vector abundance	Sporozoite rate, entomological inoculation rate (EIR)	Is the data biased by induced exophily? ¹	Is the data biased by sampling approach? ²
(country; years of intervention; refs)	Primary vector; secondary vector(s); annual EIR; insecticide resistance	Trial design; Intervention vs control; no. clusters; net material; insecticide (dose); net use	Collection methods; Collection sites, frequency	Vector density; man biting rate;	Sporozoite rate; EIR	Yes/ No/ don't know	Yes/ No/ don't know
Ghana, 1993-95 (Binka et al., 1998, Binka et al., 1996)	<i>An.gambiae</i> s.s; 100-1000; resistance not reported	cRCT; ITN (n=48) vs no net (n=48); all population; nylon; permethrin (500mg/m ²); ITN use in int areas Y1 rainy season: 97%, Y1 dry season: 65%, Y2 rainy: 72%, Y2 dry: 50%, in cont areas: NR	Ent data collected but not published				
The Gambia, 1992-93 (D'Alessandro et al., 1995a, D'Alessandro et al., 1995b, Thomson et al.,	<i>An.gambiae</i> ; <i>An.melas</i> ; 1-10; no evidence of resistance found	cRCT; ITN (treating existing nets; n=52) vs UTN/no net (n=52); existing net owners; NR; permethrin (200mg/m ²); Pre-	Paired villages representing 3 of the 5 ecological areas of The Gambia (areas II, III, V). 4 rooms for 4 nights per village	Indoor resting (mean no. females/night): Area II, Int: 2.45; Cont: 8.07 (p=0.006). Area III, Int: 6.86; Cont: 9.44 (p=0.003). Area V, Int: 3.98; Cont: 6.47	Sporozoite rate (IR & ET): Area II, Int: 0.28%; Cont: 0.36%. Area III, Int: 0.80%; Cont: 0.73%. Area V,	Yes (IR & ET only collections included in SR and EIR)	No

Table 3: Overview of available entomological evidence from clinical trials to compare personal versus community-level protection of insecticide-treated nets (ITNs)

Study	Malaria entomology	Overview of intervention	Entomological data collection	Entomological results			
				Vector abundance	Sporozoite rate, entomological inoculation rate (EIR)	Is the data biased by induced exophily? ¹	Is the data biased by sampling approach? ²
1995a, Thomson et al., 1995b)		int use of any net: 46%-79%, post-int use of ITN in int areas: 56%-94% (varied by area), in cont areas: NR	every 2 weeks; 1 room per int village with UTN as a control. Indoor spray catch, exit traps; bednet catches, outdoor human bait (HB) landing catches.	<u>Exit-trap</u> (mean no. females/night): Area II, Int: 6.38; Cont: 9.96. Area III, Int: 4.28; Cont: 5.35. Area V, Int: 1.48; Cont: 2.42	Int: 5.04%; Cont: 4.25% <u>Annual EIR</u> : Area II, Int: 0.42; Cont: 0.78. Area III, Int: 3.69; Cont: 2.79. Area V: insufficient data		
Tanzania, 1996 (Fraser-Hurt et al., 1999)	Vectors not specified; 300; resistance not reported	RCT; ITN (n=60 children) vs no net (n=60); individual allocation (0-59 mo); NR; permethrin (500mg/m ²); ITN use in int areas: 97%, UTN use in cont areas: 23%	No entomology data collected				
Cote d'Ivoire, 1999-2000 (Henry et al., 2005)	<i>An. gambiae</i> s.s.; <i>An. funestus</i> ; ?EIR; <i>An. gambiae</i> : 90% <i>kdr</i> , <i>An. funestus</i> susceptible	cRCT; ITN (n=4) vs no net (n=4); all population; NR; lambda-cyhalothrin	Ent data collected but not published	Not reported	<u>Sporozoite rate</u> : not reported <u>Annual EIR</u> : Int: 26; Cont: 55	Don't know	Don't know

Table 3: Overview of available entomological evidence from clinical trials to compare personal versus community-level protection of insecticide-treated nets (ITNs)

Study	Malaria entomology	Overview of intervention	Entomological data collection	Entomological results			
				Vector abundance	Sporozoite rate, entomological inoculation rate (EIR)	Is the data biased by induced exophily? ¹	Is the data biased by sampling approach? ²
		(15mg/m ²); ITN use in int areas: 77%-84% (varied by village), in cont areas: NR					
Thailand, 1987-88 (Kamol-Ratanakul and Prasittisuk, 1992)	<i>An. dirus</i> ; ?EIR; resistance not reported	RCT; ITN (n=131) vs UTN (n=139); individual allocation (migrant workers); nylon; permethrin (500mg/m ²); net use 70%-80% (across int & cont areas)	No entomology data collected				
Colombia, 1993-94 (Kroeger et al., 1995)	<i>An. nevai</i> ; ?EIR; no evidence of resistance found	cRCT; ITN (n=11) vs UTN (n=11); all population; polyester; lambda-hyalothrin (10-30mg/m ²); pre-int UTN use all year (int & cont): 67%-80%, treatment	No entomology data collected				

Table 3: Overview of available entomological evidence from clinical trials to compare personal versus community-level protection of insecticide-treated nets (ITNs)

Study	Malaria entomology	Overview of intervention	Entomological data collection	Entomological results			
				Vector abundance	Sporozoite rate, entomological inoculation rate (EIR)	Is the data biased by induced exophily? ¹	Is the data biased by sampling approach? ²
		uptake in int areas: 59%					
Ecuador, 1991-94 (Kroeger et al., 1995)	<i>An. albimanus</i> ; <i>An. punctimacula</i> ; <i>An. pseudopunctipennis</i> ; ?EIR; no evidence of resistance found	cRCT; ITN (n=7) vs UTN (n=7); all population; cotton; permethrin (200mg/m ²); pre-int UTN use all year (int & cont): 67%-80%, treatment uptake in int areas: 68%-80%	Ent data collected but not published	“No significant decrease in biting rates between int & cont communities.” No further detail in trial paper.	Insufficient detail in trial paper to disaggregate ent data by int/control clusters	Don’t know	Don’t know
Peru - coastal, 1991-93 (Kroeger et al., 1995)	<i>An. albimanus</i> ; <i>An. punctimacula</i> ; <i>An. pseudopunctipennis</i> ; ?EIR; no evidence of IR found; reduced pyrethroid susceptibility	cRCT; ITN (n=6) vs UTN (n=6); all population; polyester; Y1: lambda-hyalothrin (10mg/m ²) Y2: permethrin (500mg/m ²); pre-int UTN use rainy season (int & cont): 54%,	Ent data collected but not published	“No significant decrease in biting rates between int & cont communities.” No further detail in trial paper.	Insufficient detail in trial paper to disaggregate ent data by int/control clusters	Don’t know	Don’t know

Table 3: Overview of available entomological evidence from clinical trials to compare personal versus community-level protection of insecticide-treated nets (ITNs)

Study	Malaria entomology	Overview of intervention	Entomological data collection	Entomological results			
				Vector abundance	Sporozoite rate, entomological inoculation rate (EIR)	Is the data biased by induced exophily? ¹	Is the data biased by sampling approach? ²
		treatment uptake in int areas: 66%					
Peru - Amazon, 1991-92 (Kroeger et al., 1995)	<i>An. evansae</i> ; <i>An. nuneztovari</i> , <i>An. rangeli</i> ; ?EIR; no evidence of resistance found	cRCT; ITN (n=18) vs UTN (n=18); all population; polyester; cotton; permethrin (200mg/m ²); pre-int UTN use (int & cont): 67%-80%, treatment uptake in int areas: 61%	Ent data collected but not published	"No significant decrease in biting rates between int & cont communities." No further detail in trial paper.	Insufficient detail in trial paper to disaggregate ent data by int/control clusters	Don't know	Don't know
Nicaragua, 1994-96 (Kroeger et al., 1999)	<i>An. albimanus</i> ; ?EIR; some reduced pyrethroid susceptibility	cRCT; ITN (n=13) vs UTN (n=13); all population; nylon; lambda-hyalothrin (12.5mg/m ²); ITN use in int areas in Y1: 51%, outcomes in Y2 stratified by ITN use, UTN use in cont areas: 25%	Ent data collected but not published	"No significant decrease in biting rates between int & cont communities." No further detail in trial paper.	Insufficient detail in trial paper to disaggregate ent data by int/control clusters		

Table 3: Overview of available entomological evidence from clinical trials to compare personal versus community-level protection of insecticide-treated nets (ITNs)

Study	Malaria entomology	Overview of intervention	Entomological data collection	Entomological results			
				Vector abundance	Sporozoite rate, entomological inoculation rate (EIR)	Is the data biased by induced exophily? ¹	Is the data biased by sampling approach? ²
Thai-Burmese border, 1990-91 (Luxemburger et al., 1994)	<i>An. dirus</i> , <i>An. minimus</i> ; ?EIR; resistance not reported	RCT; ITN (n=175) vs UTN (n=175); individual allocation (4-15 year-olds); cotton; permethrin (500mg/m ²); 93% use (ITN in int areas, UTN in cont areas)	No entomology data collected				
Venezuela, 1999-2000 (Magris et al., 2007)	<i>An. darlingi</i> ; API: 40.3 per 1000; resistance not reported	cRCT; insecticide-treated hammock nets (ITHN; n=9) vs placebo-treated hammock nets (PTHN; n=9); all population; nylon; lambda-cyhalothrin (10mg/m ²); net use: NR	No entomology data collected				
Sierra Leone, 1992-93 (Magbity et al.,	<i>An. gambiae</i> Giles s.s.; resistance not reported	cRCT; ITN (n=8) vs no nets (n=8); nylon; all population;	Monthly samples in each study village (n=16).	<u>Human-biting rate per night</u> (12 month data) Lowland villages, Int: 1.45 (0.61-2.74); Cont: 2.16	<u>Annual sporozoite rate</u> . Lowland villages, Int: 1.8% (9/514; 0.8-3.3%);	No	No

Table 3: Overview of available entomological evidence from clinical trials to compare personal versus community-level protection of insecticide-treated nets (ITNs)

Study	Malaria entomology	Overview of intervention	Entomological data collection	Entomological results			
				Vector abundance	Sporozoite rate, entomological inoculation rate (EIR)	Is the data biased by induced exophily? ¹	Is the data biased by sampling approach? ²
1997, Marbiah et al., 1998)		lambda-cyhalothrin (10mg/m ²); net use: NR	Outdoor HB; indoor CDC light trap with UTN; window exit trap; indoor spray catch	(1.40-3.17). Highland villages, Int: 0.51 (0.26-0.82); Cont: 0.56 (0.19-1.11)	Cont: 4.1% (173/4208; 3.6-4.8%). Highland villages, Int: 0.5% (1/196; 0.01-3.0%); Cont: 7.1% (8/112; 3.1-13.6%) <u>Annual EIR</u> . Lowland villages, Int: 0.005; Cont: 0.089. Highland villages, Int: 0.003; Cont: 0.040		
Cameroon, 1992 (Moyou-Somo et al., 1995)	<i>An. gambiae</i> s.s.; ?EIR; resistance not reported	cRCT; ITN (n=2) vs no nets (n=2); all population; NR; deltamethrin (25mg/m ²); net use: NR	Ent data collected but not published; very small sample size in an urban setting				
Kenya - coastal, 1993-95 (Howard et al., 2000, Mbogo et al., 1996,	<i>An. gambiae</i> s.l.; <i>An. funestus</i> Giles; 10-30; no evidence of resistance found	cRCT; ITN (n=28) vs no nets (n=28); all population; polyester; permethrin (500mg/m ²); ITN	PSC in all int & control clusters, except 9 with more intensive ent monitoring (5 int, 4 cont).	<u>Anopheles density</u> (per sampled HH): Int: 0.22 (84/400); Cont: 2.02 (730/362). <u>Human biting rate</u> (per night). <u>Indoors</u> : Int: 23.5;	<u>Sporozoite rate</u> : Int: 4.9% (4/82); Cont: 5.0% (32/647); p>0.9 <u>Annual EIR</u> : Int: 54.1; Cont: 35.0	No	Yes

Table 3: Overview of available entomological evidence from clinical trials to compare personal versus community-level protection of insecticide-treated nets (ITNs)

Study	Malaria entomology	Overview of intervention	Entomological data collection	Entomological results			
				Vector abundance	Sporozoite rate, entomological inoculation rate (EIR)	Is the data biased by induced exophily? ¹	Is the data biased by sampling approach? ²
Nevill et al., 1996)		use by under-fives in int areas: 77% rainy season, 65% dry season, in cont areas: <1%	All 9 of these had indoor & outdoor HBC pre-int; 2 int & 1 cont post-int.	Cont: 3.7. <u>Outdoors</u> : Int: 10.2; Cont: 0.94			
Kenya – western, 1997-99 (Gimnig et al., 2003a, Gimnig et al., 2003b, Hawley et al., 2003, Phillips-Howard et al., 2003, ter Kuile et al., 2003)	<i>An. gambiae</i> Giles, <i>An. funestus</i> Giles; <i>An. arabiensis</i> ; 60-300; no evidence of resistance found	cRCT; ITN (n=113) vs no nets (n=108); all population; polyester; permethrin (500mg/m ²); ITN use in int areas: 70%, ITN ownership in cont areas: 2.6%	Quarterly mosquito collections over 2 years in 10 int & 10 cont villages randomly selected per quarter, one house randomly selected plus 9 nearest neighbours. For spatial analysis, weekly mosquito collections in 9 int, 10 cont villages. Indoor resting catches (PSC); exiting mosquito capture using "Colombian curtain"	<u>Number of fed anophelines captured indoors</u> in int villages compared to control: Any species: 71.5% lower (p<0.001); <i>An. gambiae s.l.</i> : 58.5% lower (p=0.01); <i>An. funestus</i> : 94.5% (p<0.001). <u>Exiting rates of blood-fed mosquitoes</u> in int versus control houses: <i>An. gambiae</i> : 0% versus 14.5% (p=0.32); <i>An. funestus</i> : 33% versus 4.3% (p<0.001) Significant trend for decreasing <i>An. gambiae</i> (p=0.002) and <i>An. funestus</i> (p=0.027) abundance with	<u>Sporozoite rate in int</u> versus control houses: All species: 1.2% versus 3.4% (p=0.05); <i>An. gambiae s.l.</i> : 0.8% versus 3.4% (p=0.03); <i>An. funestus</i> : 5.0% versus 3.0% (p=0.62) <u>Annual EIR</u> : estimated transmission by <i>An. gambiae</i> s.l. reduced by 91.8%, transmission by <i>An. funestus</i> reduced by 90.6% (actual numbers not reported)	Yes	No

Table 3: Overview of available entomological evidence from clinical trials to compare personal versus community-level protection of insecticide-treated nets (ITNs)

Study	Malaria entomology	Overview of intervention	Entomological data collection	Entomological results			
				Vector abundance	Sporozoite rate, entomological inoculation rate (EIR)	Is the data biased by induced exophily? ¹	Is the data biased by sampling approach? ²
				decreasing distance from int villages.			
Pakistan, 1991-92 (Rowland et al., 1996)	<i>An. culicifacies</i> , <i>An. stephensi</i> , <i>An. nigerrimus</i> , <i>An. subpictus</i> ; ?EIR; resistance not reported	RCT; ITN (n=1398) vs no nets (n=1394); HH allocation (10% refugee camp HHs); polyester; permethrin (500mg/m ²); ITN use in int areas: 73%, ITN use in cont areas: 2%	No entomology data collected				
Kenya, 1988 (Sexton et al., 1990)	<i>An. gambiae</i> ; <i>An. funestus</i> ; ?EIR; no evidence of resistance found	RCT; ITN (n=166) vs no nets (n=159); HH allocation; nylon/polyester; permethrin (500mg/m ²); ITN use in int areas: 73%, ITN use in cont areas: 2%	Weekly collections. Indoor resting only (ceiling mats in all HHs, 2-3 HHs in int and cont groups randomly selected for PSC).	<u>Proportion of HHs where anophelines collected</u> : Int: 29% (12/41); Cont: 84% (32/38).	<u>Sporozoite rate</u> : Int: too few mosquitoes; Cont: 6.4% (29/455) <u>Annual EIR</u> : not reported	Yes	No
Myanmar, 1998-99	<i>An. dirus</i> , <i>An. minimus</i> ; at least 11	cRCT; ITN (n=10) vs no nets (n=10); all	Sub-sample of Int & Cont villages, paired	Comparisons btw ITN and control villages not	Only one sporozoite positive mosquito	No	No

Table 3: Overview of available entomological evidence from clinical trials to compare personal versus community-level protection of insecticide-treated nets (ITNs)

Study	Malaria entomology	Overview of intervention	Entomological data collection	Entomological results			
				Vector abundance	Sporozoite rate, entomological inoculation rate (EIR)	Is the data biased by induced exophily? ¹	Is the data biased by sampling approach? ²
(Smithuis et al., 2013a, Smithuis et al., 2013b)	secondary species; 0.41; resistance not reported	population; polyester; deltamethrin (25mg/m ²); ITN use in int areas: 84%, UTN use in cont areas: 7%	by environmental conditions. Human bait (indoor, outdoor), exit traps, indoor resting (PSC), animal biting traps	possible due to large intra-cluster variation and insufficient number of clusters.	found across all 4866 anophelines collected (all years, int/cont villages)		
The Gambia, 1987 (Lindsay et al., 1989, Snow et al., 1988)	<i>An. gambiae</i> Giles s.s.; ?EIR; no evidence of resistance found	cRCT; ITN (n=7) vs UTN (n=9); all population; synthetic; permethrin (500mg/m ²); ITN use in int areas: 82%; UTN use in cont areas: 94%	Fortnightly collections in 2 int & 2 control villages, 10 rooms per village Indoor resting (PSC), exit traps.	<u>Number of bites/adult/season.</u> Western villages, Int: 16.9; Cont: 100.2. Eastern villages, Int: 68.7; Cont: 829.1	<u>Sporozoite rate.</u> Western villages, Int: 0.25% (1/394); Cont: 0.3% (1/350). Eastern villages, Int: 0.5% (2/422); Cont: 0.8% (8/976) <u>Season EIR.</u> Western villages, Int: 0.05; Cont: 0.4. Eastern villages, Int: 0.4; Cont: 8.9	Yes	No
Cambodia, 2001-02 (Sochantha et al., 2006)	<i>An. dirus</i> , <i>An. minimus</i> ; 6; resistance not reported	cRCT; ITN (n=17) vs no net (n=17); all population; polyester; deltamethrin	No entomology data collected				

Table 3: Overview of available entomological evidence from clinical trials to compare personal versus community-level protection of insecticide-treated nets (ITNs)

Study	Malaria entomology	Overview of intervention	Entomological data collection	Entomological results			
				Vector abundance	Sporozoite rate, entomological inoculation rate (EIR)	Is the data biased by induced exophily? ¹	Is the data biased by sampling approach? ²
		(25mg/m ²); post-int ITN use in int areas: 87%; post-int ITN use in cont areas: 14%					
<p><i>Cont = control group; cRCT = cluster randomised controlled trial; EIR = entomological inoculation rate; ent = entomological [data]; ET = exit trap; HB = human bait; HH = household; int = intervention group; IR = indoor resting; ITHN = insecticide-treated hammock net; ITN = insecticide-treated net; PSC = pyrethroid spray catch; PTHN = placebo-treated hammock net; RCT = randomised controlled trial; RR = risk ratio; SR = sporozoite rate; UTN = untreated net.</i></p> <p>¹ITNs have an excito-repellent effect i.e. encourage mosquitoes to exit a room with a treated-net. If only indoor-resting catches and exit traps are used to assess vector density and human biting rate it is likely that only a fraction of exiting mosquitoes will be captured as not all exits can be covered by traps. This may introduce bias in to the estimated efficacy of treated-nets. To avoid this bias, outdoor human landing catches should be used, or conduct collections in rooms with untreated nets in intervention villages. ²As there is often considerable ecological variation in vectors and malaria transmission between clusters, selection of sampling sites is important. To avoid bias, all clusters should be included, or if only a sample then intervention and control communities should be paired or stratified according to baseline entomological parameters.</p>							

Table 4: Overview of evidence available from randomised controlled trials to assess personal protection versus community effects of insecticide-treated nets (ITNs)

Study (country; years of intervention)	Study design	Epidemiological outcomes					Entomological outcomes					Presents evidence to assess community effect	Direction of evidence on community effect
		All-cause mortality	Clinical malaria	Parasite prevalence	Anaemia	Separate personal protection and community effects?	Vector density	Man biting rate	Sporozoite rate	EIR	Separate personal protection and community effects?		
Ghana, 1993-95 (Binka et al., 1998, Binka et al., 1996)	cRCT; ITNs vs no net	√	X	X	X	√	X	X	X	X	X	Yes (epi only)	For (epi only)
The Gambia, 1992-93 (D'Alessandro et al., 1995a, D'Alessandro et al., 1995b, Thomson et al., 1995a, Thomson et al., 1995b)	cRCT; ITN vs UTN or no net	√	X	√	X	√	√	√	√	√	√	Yes (epi & ent)	Against (epi & ent)
Tanzania, 1996 (Fraser-Hurt et al., 1999)	RCT; ITN vs no net	X	X	√	√	X	X	X	X	X	X	No	
Cote d'Ivoire, 1999-2000 (Henry et al., 2005)	cRCT; ITN vs no net	X	√	√	√	X	X	X	X	√	?	No	
Thailand, 1987-88 (Kamol-Ratanakul and Prasittisuk, 1992)	RCT, ITN vs UTN	X	√	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	No	
Colombia, 1993-94 (Kroeger et al., 1995)	cRCT; ITN vs UTN	X	√	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	No	

Table 4: Overview of evidence available from randomised controlled trials to assess personal protection versus community effects of insecticide-treated nets (ITNs)

Study (country; years of intervention)	Study design	Epidemiological outcomes					Entomological outcomes					Presents evidence to assess community effect	Direction of evidence on community effect
		All-cause mortality	Clinical malaria	Parasite prevalence	Anaemia	Separate personal protection and community effects?	Vector density	Man biting rate	Sporozoite rate	EIR	Separate personal protection and community effects?		
Ecuador, 1991-94 (Kroeger et al., 1995)	cRCT; ITN vs UTN	X	√	X	X	X	√	√	√	X	X	No	
Peru - coastal, 1991-93 (Kroeger et al., 1995)	cRCT; ITN vs UTN	X	√	X	X	X	√	√	√	X	X	No	
Peru - Amazon, 1991-92 (Kroeger et al., 1995)	cRCT; ITN vs UTN	X	√	X	X	X	√	√	√	X	X	No	
Nicaragua, 1994-96 (Kroeger et al., 1999)	cRCT; ITN vs UTN	X	√	X	X	X	√	√	√	X	X	No	
Thai-Burmese border, 1990-91 (Luxemburger et al., 1994)	RCT; ITN vs UTN	X	√	√	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	No	
Venezuela, 1999-2000 (Magris et al., 2007)	cRCT; ITN vs UTN	X	√	√	√	X	X	X	X	X	X	No	
Sierra Leone, 1992-93 (Magbity et al., 1997, Marbiah et al., 1998)	cRCT; ITN vs no nets	X	√	X	√	X	X	√	√	√	√	Yes (ent only)	For (ent)
Cameroon, 1992 (Moyou-Somo et al., 1995)	cRCT; ITN vs no nets	X	X	√	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	No	

Table 4: Overview of evidence available from randomised controlled trials to assess personal protection versus community effects of insecticide-treated nets (ITNs)

Study (country; years of intervention)	Study design	Epidemiological outcomes					Entomological outcomes					Presents evidence to assess community effect	Direction of evidence on community effect
		All-cause mortality	Clinical malaria	Parasite prevalence	Anaemia	Separate personal protection and community effects?	Vector density	Man biting rate	Sporozoite rate	EIR	Separate personal protection and community effects?		
Kenya - coastal, 1993-95 (Howard et al., 2000, Mbogo et al., 1996, Nevill et al., 1996)	cRCT; ITN vs no nets	√	√ severe	X	X	√	√	√	√	√	√	Yes (epi & ent)	For (epi; ent inconclusive)
Kenya – western, 1997-99 (Gimnig et al., 2003a, Gimnig et al., 2003b, Hawley et al., 2003, Phillips-Howard et al., 2003, ter Kuile et al., 2003)	cRCT; ITN vs no nets	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	Yes (epi & ent)	For (epi & ent)
Pakistan, 1991-92 (Rowland et al., 1996)	RCT; ITN vs no net	X	√	√	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	No	
Kenya, 1988 (Sexton et al., 1990)	RCT; ITN vs no net	X	√	X	X	X	√	√	√	X	X	No	
Myanmar, 1998-99 (Smithuis et al., 2013a, Smithuis et al., 2013b)	cRCT; ITN vs no net	X	√	√	√	X	√	√	√	√	X	No	
The Gambia, 1987 (Lindsay et al., 1989, Snow et al., 1988)	cRCT; ITN vs UTN	X	√	√	√	X	√	√	√	√	√	Yes (ent only)	Against (ent)
Cambodia, 2001-02 (Sochantha et al., 2006)	cRCT; ITN vs no net	X	√	√	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	No	

Table 5: Overview of epidemiological and entomological evidence for a community effect of ITNs from studies reporting results directly addressing the review question

Study	Context	Overview of intervention	Epidemiological results	Risk of bias ¹	Entomological results	Risk of bias ²	Evidence for a community effect
Ghana, 1993-95 (Binka et al., 1998, Binka et al., 1996)	High, seasonal transmission (EIR: 100-1000); Main vector: <i>An. gambiae</i> s.s.; IR not reported; ITN use in int areas Y1 rainy season: 97%, Y1 dry season: 65%, Y2 rainy: 72%, Y2 dry: 50%, in cont areas: NR	cRCT; ITN (n=48) vs no net (n=48); all population; nylon; permethrin (500mg/m ²)	<u>All-cause mortality rate</u> amongst non-users (in control HHs) increased with distance from nearest HH with ITNs (p=0.007). Each increase of 100m away from the boundary associated with an increased mortality risk of individuals without ITNs of 6.7% (1.8-11.4%).	Low risk			Present (epi only)
The Gambia, 1992-93 (D'Alessandro et al., 1995a, D'Alessandro et al., 1995b, Thomson et al., 1995a, Thomson et al., 1995b)	Moderate, seasonal transmission (EIR: 1-10); Main vectors: <i>An. gambiae</i> , <i>An. melas</i> ; No evidence of IR found; Pre-int use of any net: 46%-79%, post-int use of ITN in int areas: 67% (varied by area: 56%-94%), in cont areas: NR	cRCT; ITN (treating existing nets; n=52) vs UTN/no net (n=52); existing net owners; NR; permethrin (200mg/m ²)	<i>P. falciparum</i> PR: ITN users, Int clusters: 27%, UTN users, Int: 22%; Cont: 30%; No net, Int: 60%; Cont: 45%	Low risk	<u>Indoor resting</u> (mean no. females/night): Area II, Int: 2.45; Cont: 8.07 (p=0.006). Area III, Int: 6.86; Cont: 9.44 (p=0.003). Area V, Int: 3.98; Cont: 6.47 <u>Exit-trap</u> (mean no. females/night): Area II, Int: 6.38; Cont: 9.96. Area III, Int: 4.28; Cont: 5.35. Area V, Int: 1.48; Cont: 2.42 <u>Sporozoite rate</u> (IR & ET): Area II, Int: 0.28% (4/1298); Cont: 0.36% (9/2472). Area III, Int: 0.80% (21/2693); Cont: 0.73% (34/4720). Area V, Int: 5.04% (35/689); Cont: 4.25% (49/1158) <u>Annual EIR</u> : Area II, Int: 0.42; Cont: 0.78. Area III, Int: 3.69; Cont: 2.79. Area V: insufficient data	Risk of bias (in some outcomes) due to induced exophily	Absent (epi & ent)
Sierra Leone, 1992-93 (Magbity et al., 1997,	Hyperendemic, perennial (EIR: 21-35); <i>Main vector: An. gambiae</i> Giles s.s.; IR	cRCT; ITN (n=8) vs no nets (n=8); nylon; all population;			<u>Human-biting rate per night</u> (12 month data) Lowland villages, Int: 1.45 (0.61-2.74); Cont: 2.16 (1.40-3.17). Highland villages, Int: 0.51 (0.26-0.82); Cont: 0.56 (0.19-1.11)	Low risk	Present (ent)

Table 5: Overview of epidemiological and entomological evidence for a community effect of ITNs from studies reporting results directly addressing the review question

Study	Context	Overview of intervention	Epidemiological results	Risk of bias ¹	Entomological results	Risk of bias ²	Evidence for a community effect
Marbiah et al., 1998)	not reported; Net use: NR	lambda-cyhalothrin (10mg/m ²)			<u>Annual sporozoite rate</u> . Lowland villages, Int: 1.8% (9/514; 0.8-3.3%); Cont: 4.1% (173/4208; 3.6-4.8%). Highland villages, Int: 0.5% (1/196; 0.01-3.0%); Cont: 7.1% (8/112; 3.1-13.6%) <u>Annual EIR</u> . Lowland villages, Int: 0.005; Cont: 0.089. Highland villages, Int: 0.003; Cont: 0.040		
Kenya - coastal, 1993-95 (Howard et al., 2000, Mbogo et al., 1996, Nevill et al., 1996)	Moderate seasonal transmission (EIR: 10-30); Main vectors: <i>An. gambiae</i> s.l., <i>An. funestus</i> Giles; No evidence of IR found; ITN use by under-fives in int areas: 77% rainy season, 65% dry season, in cont areas: <1%	cRCT; ITN (n=28) vs no nets (n=28); all population; polyester; permethrin (500mg/m ²)	<u>Severe malaria admissions</u> (1-59mo), cohort analysis: Int clusters: ITN users: 5.8% (95/1626), non-ITN users: 7.3% (13/179), p>0.05; Cont clusters: 12.6% (257/2048); non-ITN users in int clusters: 7.3% (13/179) (p=0.05)	Low risk	<u>Anopheles density</u> (per sampled HH): Int: 0.22 (84/400); Cont: 2.02 (730/362). <u>Human biting rate</u> (per night). <u>Indoors</u> : Int: 23.5; Cont: 3.7. <u>Outdoors</u> : Int: 10.2; Cont: 0.94 <u>Sporozoite rate</u> : Int: 4.9% (4/82); Cont: 5.0% (32/647); p>0.9 <u>Annual EIR</u> : Int: 54.1; Cont: 35.0	Risk of bias due to sampling approach	Present (epi; ent inconclusive)
Kenya – western, 1997-99 (Gimnig et al., 2003a, Gimnig et al., 2003b, Hawley et al., 2003, Phillips-Howard et al., 2003, ter	Intense perennial transmission (EIR: 60-300); Main vectors: <i>An. gambiae</i> Giles, <i>An. funestus</i> Giles; <i>An. arabiensis</i> ; No evidence of IR found; ITN use in int areas: 70%, ITN ownership in cont areas: 2.6%	cRCT; ITN (n=113) vs no nets (n=108); all population; polyester; permethrin (500mg/m ²)	<u>Child mortality, moderate anaemia, high-density parasitaemia, HB levels</u> : protective effect in control HHs located within 300m of an ITN HH. Strength of community effect depended on at least moderate coverage with ITNs in neighbouring HHs (>50%).	Low risk (mortality outcome) High risk (morbidity outcomes) ³	<u>Number of fed anophelines captured indoors</u> in int villages compared to control: Any species: 71.5% lower (p<0.001); <i>An. gambiae</i> s.l.: 58.5% lower (p=0.01); <i>An. funestus</i> : 94.5% (p<0.001). Significant trend for decreasing <i>An. gambiae</i> (p=0.002) and <i>An. funestus</i> (p=0.027) abundance with decreasing distance from int villages. <u>Sporozoite rate</u> in int versus control houses: All species: 1.2% versus 3.4% (p=0.05); <i>An. gambiae</i> s.l.: 0.8% versus 3.4% (p=0.03); <i>An. funestus</i> :	Risk of bias due to induced exophily	Present (epi & ent)

Table 5: Overview of epidemiological and entomological evidence for a community effect of ITNs from studies reporting results directly addressing the review question

Study	Context	Overview of intervention	Epidemiological results	Risk of bias ¹	Entomological results	Risk of bias ²	Evidence for a community effect
Kuile et al., 2003)					5.0% versus 3.0% (p=0.62). n/N not specified by int/cont. <u>Annual EIR</u> : estimated transmission by <i>An. gambiae</i> s.l. reduced by 91.8%, transmission by <i>An. funestus</i> reduced by 90.6% (actual numbers not reported)		
The Gambia, 1987 (Lindsay et al., 1989, Snow et al., 1988)	Moderate seasonal transmission (EIR: 24); Main vector: <i>An. gambiae</i> Giles s.s.; No evidence of IR found; ITN use in int areas: 82%; UTN use in cont areas: 94%	cRCT; ITN (n=7) vs UTN (n=9); all population; synthetic; permethrin (500mg/m ²)			<u>Number of bites/adult/season</u> . Western villages, Int: 16.9; Cont: 100.2. Eastern villages, Int: 68.7; Cont: 829.1 <u>Sporozoite rate</u> . Western villages, Int: 0.25% (1/394); Cont: 0.3% (1/350). Eastern villages, Int: 0.5% (2/422); Cont: 0.8% (8/976); Int vs Cont p=0.13 <u>Season EIR</u> . Western villages, Int: 0.05; Cont: 0.4. Eastern villages, Int: 0.4; Cont: 8.9	Risk of bias due to induced exophily	Absent (ent)

Abbreviations: cont = control group; cRCT = cluster randomised controlled trial; ent = entomological; epi = epidemiological; Hb = haemoglobin; HH = household; int = intervention group; ITN = insecticide-treated net; mo = months-old; NR = not reported; PR = parasite prevalence; UTN = untreated net; Y1 (etc.) = year 1.

¹Overall risk of bias of the epidemiological outcomes is based on overall judgement of seven domains of bias (see Table 4 for details). ²Bias of entomological outcomes based on assessment of whether vector sampling methods could lead to bias due to induced exophily, and whether selection of sampling sites could lead to selection bias (see Table 2 for further details). ³Main mortality trial included children aged 1 to 59 months, but only children aged <36 months were sampled for the morbidity analysis; therefore morbidity outcomes are at risk of bias due to incomplete outcome data.

Table 6: Rating the certainty of evidence for a community effect of ITNs from studies reporting results directly addressing the review question

GRADE domain	Judgement	Concerns about certainty domains
Risk of bias	Low risk of bias for all four studies contributing epidemiological data (Binka et al., 1996, D'Alessandro et al., 1995a, Nevill et al., 1996, Phillips-Howard et al., 2003). Substantial risk of bias in some outcome measures from the entomological studies due to the methods of mosquito capture. However overall, we can have reasonable confidence in the entomological evidence from four of the five studies considered (Gimnig et al., 2003a, Gimnig et al., 2003b, Lindsay et al., 1989, Magbity et al., 1997, Thomson et al., 1995a, Thomson et al., 1995b), but not the other two (Lindsay et al., 1989, Mbogo et al., 1996).	Not serious (epi outcomes); Moderate (ent outcomes)
Indirectness	The intervention, comparators and analyses in the studies included in the data synthesis all provide direct evidence to separate the community effect of ITNs from personal protection	Not serious
Imprecision	All studies included in the data synthesis were cRCTs. There was a total of 477 clusters across the four studies contributing epidemiological outcomes. Precision of clinical outcomes therefore not a concern, including disaggregating data e.g. for spatial analysis. The scale of data collection varied across the five studies contributing entomological data in terms of number of sites and frequency of data collection. A total of 22,861 mosquitoes were examined for sporozoites across four of the five studies that reported this measure (range: 729 to 13,030) with a total of 391 positive (range: 12 to 191). Low numbers of sporozoite positive mosquitoes can result in low power to detect a difference between intervention and control areas. This may be the case for two of the five entomology studies (coastal Kenya, The Gambia (Lindsay) where a p-value >0.05 may be due to a lack of power.	Not serious (epi outcomes); Moderate (ent outcomes)
Inconsistency	Overall, four of the six studies reported presence of epidemiological and/or entomological evidence for a community effect. Evidence of a community effect was absent for two studies from The Gambia. However, given the underlying ento-epidemiological theory for how ITNs work, the variation in evidence of community effect is neither unexpected or a cause for concern regarding the certainty of evidence. The contexts of the studies in terms of transmission intensity, vector behaviour, ITN use, spatial distribution of intervention and control clusters and insecticide resistance will all influence the size of community effect.	Not serious
Publication bias	We did not strongly suspect publication bias because studies with both positive and negative findings regarding the presence of a community effect were published, and the search for studies was comprehensive.	Not suspected
Factors that raise certainty in evidence	<i>Epidemiological and entomological evidence converge:</i> three of the six studies had both epidemiological and entomological outcomes suitable to assess evidence of a community effect. In the case of western Kenya, evidence for a community effect was present in both types of outcome; in the Gambia, evidence for a community effect was absent in both; in coastal Kenya strong epidemiological	

	<p>evidence was present but methodological limitations make the entomological evidence inconclusive. Of the other three studies, one reported only epidemiological outcomes and two reported only entomological outcomes relevant to the community effect question.</p> <p><i>Dose-response gradient:</i> three studies reported evidence for a dose response between decreasing proximity of ITN non-users to ITN users and decreased community effect (Binka et al., 1998, Hawley et al., 2003, Howard et al., 2000); two of these studies also reported evidence for a dose response between increasing ITN use and increased community effect (Hawley et al., 2003, Howard et al., 2000).</p>	
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